

ARCTIC PASSION

Deliverable 1.8

Recent progress and ways forward
for Arctic observing capacities

Version 1

15 November 2025

101003472 | Arctic PASSION

Work package

WP1 - ESTABLISHING AN ADAPTIVE AND MORE COMPLETE ARCTIC OBSERVING SYSTEM

Lead beneficiary

Norwegian Polar Institute (WP1)
UiT The Arctic University of Norway (Task 1.3)

Lead authors

Anna Nikolopoulos (UiT) and Arild Sundfjord (NPI)

Contributing authors (in alphabetical order of their institutions)

Anna Irrgang, Tillmann Lübker, and Marcel Nicolaus	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI), Germany
Maribeth S. Murray	Arctic Institute of North America, University of Calgary (AINA), Canada
Andrew Flemming	British Antarctic survey (BAS), United Kingdom
Gorm Dybkjær, Steffen M. Olsen	Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), Denmark
Ilaria Crotti, Srđan Dobricic	EC Joint Research Centre (JRC-ISPRA), Italy
Kirsikka Heinilä	Finnish Environment Institute (FEI/Syke), Finland
Katriina Veijola	Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI), Finland
Malene Simon Hegelund	Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR), Greenland
Caroline Coch, Margareta Johansson	INTERACT Non-Profit Association (INPA), Sweden
Vito Vitale	Italian National Research Council, Institute of Polar Sciences (CNR-ISP), Italy
Nuncio Murukesh	National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research (NCPOR), India
Øystein Godøy	Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET), Norway
Sebastian Gerland, Mats Granskog	Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI), Norway
Ilkka Matero, Heikki Lihavainen	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SIOS), Norway
Tero Mustonen	Snowchange Cooperative (Snowchange), Finland
Marit Reigstad, Bodil Bluhm	UiT The Arctic University of Norway (UiT), Norway
Tian Li, Jonathan Bamber	University of Bristol (UBristol), United Kingdom

Status: Final (v1)

Dissemination level: PUBLIC

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003472

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Land and Land ice.....	7
2.1. Community Based Monitoring and Citizen Science.....	7
2.2. Land Monitoring Sites	9
2.3. Wildfire: Definition of Shared Arctic Variables	11
2.4. Wildfire: Web mapping service (Arctic Service <i>INFRA</i>)	12
2.5. Permafrost: Observing best practices.....	13
2.6. Permafrost: Land surface change (Arctic Service <i>ALEX</i>)	14
2.7. Permafrost: Definition of Shared Arctic Variables	15
2.8. Lake Ice Arctic Service	17
2.9. Land ice	19
3. Ocean and Sea ice	22
3.1. Ocean: In situ observations	23
3.2. Sea ice: In situ observations	25
3.3. Sea Ice: Remote sensing activities	28
3.4. Sea ice: Shipping Safety (Arctic Service <i>POLARIS</i>)	29
3.5. Sea Ice: Definition of Shared Arctic Variables	30
3.6. Distributed Biological Observatories	31
3.7. Coastal community-based monitoring (Arctic Service)	34
4. Atmosphere	36
4.1. Air Quality (Arctic Service <i>AURORAE</i>).....	36
4.2. WMO GTS datasets made available.....	38
4.3. Radiation observations over the ocean	399
5. Establishing a comprehensive Arctic observing system	42
5.1. Priorities for enhancing Arctic observations	43
5.2. Technical and practical solutions.....	45
5.3. Organisational improvements	47
5.4. Long-term sustainability.....	49
Appendix 1. References	51
Appendix 2. Abbreviations, Acronyms and Links.....	55

The institutions indicated for each section in Chapter 2-4 were the leading partners for each activity, and contributors to this report.

Within the text, () indicate references, either to project deliverables or to general references, while [] refer to related sections in this report.

URL links are generally not included in the free text but instead given in Appendix 2.

Executive Summary

This report presents the progress and insights from the observational activities in the EU Horizon 2020 Arctic PASSION project and offers recommendations for advancing a long-term, integrated observing system that better supports societal needs, scientific understanding, and informed decision-making in a time of rapid environmental change.

The observation-related tasks of the project spanned the interconnected domains of Land/Land ice, Ocean/Sea ice, and Atmosphere. These efforts brought together diverse partners and perspectives to assess current practices, identify gaps, and propose practical steps toward a more coordinated, inclusive, and sustainable Arctic observing system that delivers data of the necessary relevance, quality, and accessibility. In doing so, the project also contributed to closing some of the identified gaps, through targeted activities, strengthened collaborations, and shared learning.

A central message from our work is that **long-term, internationally coordinated funding is essential**—not only to maintain existing monitoring efforts, but to develop Arctic observing systems that are responsive to societal needs and capable of supporting operational services and long-term planning.

We also highlight the need to **improve information flow across the full data lifecycle**—from planning and observing to data processing, analysis, sharing, and synthesis. Strengthening these connections will help ensure that Arctic observations are accessible, relevant, and actionable for a wide range of users.

While many valuable observations are already being made, they still remain fragmented, short-term, or difficult to access and integrate. To address these challenges, we recommend:

- **Sustaining and expanding long-term observations** across disciplines and regions to ensure continuity in tracking and understanding the rapid ongoing changes in the Arctic climate, environment and ecosystems.
- **Fostering collaboration and shared commitments** among nations, communities, and organizations to reduce fragmentation, optimize resources, ensure timely data sharing and increase impact.
- **Continuing to harmonise data collection and processing, and strengthen open, user-friendly data platforms** that meet **FAIR** and **CARE** principles. This will enhance data accessibility and reusability, improve complementarity across observing system components, facilitate data use for validation, and ensure that Arctic data is used and shared in accordance with the rights and interests of Indigenous Peoples and other data rights holders.

Further detail and context behind these recommendations, along with a number of more specific suggestions for action, are presented in the full report.

1. Introduction

The key motivation behind Arctic PASSION (EU Horizon 2020 project; <https://arcticpassion.eu>) has been to contribute to the co-creation and implementation of a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system. By refining operability, expanding pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and improving inclusion of Indigenous and local knowledge systems, the aim has been to overcome known shortcomings in the present observing system. Arctic PASSION has also worked to streamline the access and interoperability of Arctic data systems and services, and to strengthen the economic viability and sustainability of the observing system.

Arctic PASSION consisted of ten work packages dedicated to different aspects of the Arctic observing system. Most of the project's observational activities were carried out within Work Package 1 (WP1; *Establishing an adaptive and more complete Arctic observing system*) which aimed to develop an inclusive and integrative framework of observations for a comprehensive Arctic observing system of systems, i.e., across components and domains. These efforts focused on coordinating, enhancing and building upon existing observing infrastructures and networks to provide the most vital observations for understanding how the Arctic system functions and evolves. Several of the Arctic Services developed within Work Package 4 (WP4; *Innovating user-driven Arctic EuroGEO services*) also depended on observation-related inputs. These Arctic services were established to increase the flow of information and knowledge in areas of societal and economic relevance presently inadequately served: Food security, Emergency preparedness, Wildfire and pollution risk reduction, Environmental change information and infrastructure, Transport and safe shipping. Their development followed priorities of the Arctic Council and its Working Groups, the Arctic Science Ministerial, and the Arctic Observing Summit.

Figure 1. Land-Sea-Air cross-section illustrating the observational components in Arctic PASSION, undertaken mainly in Work Packages 1 and 4. The numbers refer to the sections in Chapters 2-4. The Arctic Services and data produced in the project are available through <https://arcticpassion.eu/data/> or through the individual references listed in Appendix 2 (Image courtesy of H. Abbas/GridA).

As the concluding deliverable for WP1, this report summarizes progress and experiences made in Arctic PASSION regarding Arctic observational activities (primarily in WP1 but also in WP4) and provides our recommendations for how to move further towards establishing a holistic long-term observing system serving societal needs and meeting continuing and emerging challenges. These recommendations build on, and expand, existing Arctic-focused roadmap processes, addressing immediate gaps and longer-term targets to enhance the observing system across disciplines, considering societal needs, operational services, and long-term management.

We focus on activities for obtaining the observations as such (*observing methodologies*, including their coordination). By observing methodologies, we mean all types of observing and knowledge systems; *in situ* (on site), *remote sensing* (satellite), *Community-Based Monitoring (CBM)*, *Indigenous and local knowledge*. Other factors crucial for building and operating the end-to-end observing system like data management, production of services, end-user uptake, and funding systems are beyond the scope of this report; they are rather the focus of Work Package 8 and deliverable report '*Final Synthesis and Roadmap for further evolution of the pan-AOSS*' (D8.2) with its approach on the observing system in its entirety.

The Arctic PASSION contributions to this observational scope, and lessons learned, are first summarized in Chapters 2-4 as components in their natural domain (Land/Land ice, Ocean/Sea ice, and Atmosphere; Figure 1). The concluding Chapter 5 highlights our key messages from these outlined activities with onward recommendations regarding *Priorities for enhancing observations* [5.1], *Technical solutions* to overcome observing challenges [5.2], and *Organisational improvements* resolving fragmentation across the system components themselves, as well as across of nations, communities and organizations [5.3], while aiming to improve the *Long-term sustainability* [5.4]. In Chapter 5 we also relate our key messages to recommendations made by other recent projects (e.g., KEPLER, INTAROS) and organizations (e.g., EU PolarNet-2, Copernicus Polar Task Force). While reference literature is cited throughout the text, web links to sources are compiled in Appendix 2 - *Abbreviations, Acronyms and Links*.

2. Land and Land ice

Arctic PASSION has aimed to unite, expand, and improve existing systems for monitoring key Arctic climate and ecosystem variables. For the terrestrial domain, WP1 served to explore how Community Based Monitoring (CBM) networks can expand observations, improve baselines, identify new indicators, and monitor local impacts, in a sustainable way [2.1]. WP1 also expanded and harmonised terrestrial monitoring through the INTERACT network [2.2].

In support of the Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS) process, the identification and implementation of Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) were key elements in the Arctic PASSION project. The objective was to define SAVs on Wildfire [2.3], Permafrost [2.7], and for the marine realm Sea Ice [3.7], representing three of the broader areas of concern in Arctic monitoring and decision-making (Starkweather et al., 2021). The SAV definition work followed ROADS and the input from participants in the biennial Arctic Observing Summits (AOS), acknowledging shared benefits of the observing system as an essential guiding principle. The process was shared between WP1 and WP6 and helped identify current and additional observational needs across themes through Expert Panels and open workshops (D1.2; D6.3).

Arctic PASSION WP4 served to create a set of pilot Arctic Services, and several of these were related to the terrestrial scope. Within the theme of Wildfire, the INFRA web mapping service was developed to facilitate the access to relevant information from diverse sources and products [2.4]. For Permafrost, the Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX) portal was developed and successfully launched, providing interactive maps of recent information on land surface changes, hot spots of disturbance, and potential areas of active permafrost thaw and erosion [2.6]. The work with this Permafrost Arctic Service also led to the development and publication of best practice guidelines for permafrost measurements, as part of WMO Guide No.8. The Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety addressed the demand for a more unified and accessible system for lake ice conditions by integrating Earth Observation-derived data, in situ measurements from governmental networks, and community-based monitoring [2.8].

With respect to Land ice, Arctic PASSION focused on variables not adequately covered through existing programmes, primarily coordinated by ESA. Focus was on Meltwater production and runoff, and Iceberg calving fluxes - two components that have significant impacts on the climate system as well as on activities crucial to coastal communities such as ship traffic and fisheries [2.9]. An important task in this work was to produce operational data pipelines with data flexibility and redundancy built in, to make the workflow independent of single point failures.

2.1. Community Based Monitoring and Citizen Science

Snowchange Cooperative (Snowchange)

2.1.1. Background

Through community-based monitoring initiatives, Arctic residents conduct or are involved in ongoing observing and monitoring activities. Arctic Indigenous Peoples have been observing the environment for millennia, and this type of monitoring often incorporates Indigenous knowledge and traditional knowledge, which may be used independently from or in partnership with formal scientific monitoring methods.

The role and applications of CBM have existed in the Arctic for decades. The wider adoption of these systems that embrace, support and engage with the Indigenous Peoples and local observations largely has happened because of the Indigenous land claims and other equity mechanisms in the North American Arctic. It is important to recognize that "Arctic observing" and CBM are built on a history of non-Arctic infrastructures and institutions.

2.1.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

A broader assessment, by a network of Indigenous and local communities across the Arctic (D1.1; Snowchange cooperative) highlighted gaps in Arctic observations, including spatial and temporal scales of change and diverse knowledge systems. The assessment specifically aimed to address divergence in CBM observations across the Arctic and explore how CBM networks can expand observational coverage, strengthen baselines, identify and monitor new indicators and local impacts, and ensure the sustainability of CBM initiatives.

The focus of the assessment was on structural frameworks and gaps in inclusion mechanisms, for example initiatives created beyond the commonly represented North American Arctic region, the role of nomadic societies in CBM, and culturally grounded practices and rights.

A combination of methods was used to identify and address the gaps in CBM work; literature surveys, documentation of Indigenous best practices, targeted evaluations (e.g., ICC 2015; Holmberg, 2022) and a set of community examples from Arctic PASSION Indigenous partners. These examples were successively expanded to a pan-regional context, under awareness that the divergence across geographies remains an issue. Also, since 2022 the Russian war on Ukraine has altered the Russian CBM efforts and our capacity to connect about the situation and progress made there.

In parallel to this work, the Arctic Service *Event Database of Community Based Monitoring* was created. This is a co-developed database of socio-ecologically relevant events focusing on significant ecosystem changes. The database includes oral/linguistic, temporal and spatial scales and dimensions, including those unique to Indigenous Knowledge and Local Knowledge. In doing so, it strengthens and diversifies monitoring capacity and supports adaptation and risk mitigation. The service is available through the Snowchange Arctic Seas portal [Appendix 2].

2.1.3. Ways forward

Arctic community-based monitoring in the 2020s is being reshaped by the combined forces of accelerating change in natural ecosystems, climate, and weather, alongside an increasing reliance on technology. These dynamics are influencing how Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents observe, interpret, and respond to their environments.

Going forward, it is important to remain aware of past assumptions and problems associated with CBM efforts and to learn from them. Additionally, the Russian war on Ukraine has altered the methods of inter-community exchanges, for example under the Arctic Council and many other fora.

To keep advancing the pan-Arctic observational system, CBM should be increasingly utilized for addressing shortcomings in instrument-based observation system across the marine, atmospheric, cryosphere and terrestrial domains (D1.1). Priority should be given to the following actions:

- **Expand community-based monitoring of change** through observations led by those with deep cultural and local knowledge. This includes capturing signals outside formal systems such as smaller seismic events, past extreme weather, and species migrations, and establishing mechanisms to highlight "significant change" as interpreted by CBM co-researchers.

- **Ensure ethical collaboration** by implementing Free, Prior and Informed Consent (FPIC), respecting intellectual property rights, and safeguarding ownership of shared observations. These practices build trust and reinforce the validity of Indigenous contributions.
- **Dialogue with Indigenous knowledge** through respectful exploration of hindcasting methods for historical records, place names, and gendered ways of knowing, together with the concept of “Arctic Crashes” (Krupnik et al. 2020) as potential indicators of regime shifts and tipping points. This approach helps identify areas of convergence and divergence between scientific and Indigenous perspectives.

2.2. Land Monitoring Sites

INTERACT Non-Profit Association (INPA)

2.2.1. Background

The effort to connect terrestrial Arctic research sites dates to the 1960s, when the International Biological Programme (IBP) linked researchers and sites across the tundra biome. The programme (1964–1974) included participants from Canada, the United States, and the western Soviet Union during the ongoing Cold War (Bliss et al. 1981).

A network of nine research stations around the North Atlantic, SCANNET, was initiated by former IBP participants with the objective of monitoring environmental changes in real time. The four-year SCANNET project was funded under the EU's 5th Framework Programme (Callaghan et al., 2004).

Although SCANNET's funding eventually ended, collaboration among the stations continued, and new sites joined the network based on three criteria: 1) long-term stability, with secured operation year-round and from year to year, 2) multidisciplinary activities, and 3) the capacity to host visiting scientists. By 2011, the network had grown to 33 stations across 12 countries and secured EU funding under the 7th Framework Programme, becoming INTERACT. Its aim was to create a comprehensive infrastructure for Arctic terrestrial research, including boreal and alpine stations. The network expanded to 77 stations by 2016 (marking the start of INTERACT's second funding phase) and to 86 stations in 2020 with the third phase supported by EU Horizon 2020 funding. By early 2022, over 90 stations were part of INTERACT, collectively hosting more than 15,000 scientists annually and contributing to over 150 international networks. Due to the Russian invasion of Ukraine, collaboration with 21 Russian stations was suspended (Johansson and Callaghan, 2025).

To ensure long-term sustainability beyond EU funding, members of the INTERACT Steering Committee established the INTERACT Non-Profit Association (INPA) in 2020. When the INTERACT project formally ended in late 2024, all stations joined INPA, which continues to support a network of Arctic, sub-Arctic, boreal, and alpine research infrastructures (Johansson and Callaghan, 2025).

To improve data accessibility and support remote research, INTERACT launched a dedicated Data Portal in 2021, offering free virtual access (VA) to metadata and datasets from participating stations. By the end of 2024, 18 stations provided VA through the portal, which hosted over 1,900 datasets, ranging from near real-time observations to digitized historical records. The portal enables online discovery and use of Arctic environmental data, aligning with FAIR data principles and promoting open science.

2.2.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Arctic PASSION has advanced the INTERACT Arctic observing efforts by strengthening existing monitoring sites and establishing new ones over ten representative land locations across diverse ecosystems and permafrost zones, laying the foundation for long-term climate system studies. A key outcome is the collaborative identification of Priority Parameters. They encompass meteorological parameters (air temperature, air humidity, air pressure, wind velocity, wind direction, precipitation), energy balance and radiation (short wave incoming radiation, short wave outgoing radiation, long wave incoming radiation, long wave outgoing radiation, net radiation, UV-B, sensible heat flux, latent heat flux, soil heat flux), sub surface characteristics (permafrost/ground temperature, ground surface temperature, soil temperature, active layer thickness), and snow characteristics (snow depth, snow density, snow temperature). These parameters are also of relevance to the Shared Arctic Variable themes of wildfire and permafrost degradation are tackled in Arctic PASSION.

To address existing gaps in monitoring these parameters, Arctic PASSION funded the acquisition of instrumentation, enhancing the coverage and comparability of observations across the ten sites. In 2025, a dedicated workshop was organized to foster knowledge exchange on instrumentation use, data practices, and site-specific adaptations to Arctic conditions. This event also served to engage additional stations in the process, broadening participation and disseminating best practices developed during the project.

In addition to these advances, the project identified ongoing challenges in harmonising data collection, largely due to differences in station setups. When national meteorological services operate key infrastructure, research stations or external projects may have limited ability to adjust, calibrate, or access the equipment. Technical hurdles like inconsistent documentation, limited staff availability, and constraints through the short field season highlighted the need for robust planning, maintenance funding, and capacity building. Importantly, knowledge exchange among stations - on data practices, instrument setups, and adapting to Arctic conditions - emerged as a legacy of the project that will continue to strengthen the observing system beyond Arctic PASSION.

2.2.3. Ways forward

The successful implementation of the Arctic PASSION terrestrial monitoring sites - guided by using a shared set of Priority Parameters - demonstrates the value of focusing efforts on key indicators of climate change such as permafrost degradation and wildfires. To build on this momentum, future systems must invest in continued harmonisation of measurements while respecting site-specific constraints, particularly where integrating new instruments into nationally managed infrastructure remains complex. Future standardisation of observations of more complex ecosystem indicators would benefit from building on lessons learned from the implementation of harmonised monitoring of key climate variables.

Enhanced support for capacity-building, maintenance, and technical coordination is essential, alongside innovations such as AI-assisted data quality checks and automation.

Long-term sustainability will also depend on making data both interoperable and publicly accessible, as well as securing funding to maintain equipment over time. Arctic PASSION has demonstrated that virtual access and metadata standardisation are achievable through dialogue and mutual learning. Continued support for such collaborative networks is critical to improving data quality and coverage. INTERACT was established as a non-profit association in 2021 to provide a sustainable platform for long-term collaboration among Arctic, alpine and boreal research stations. It is working towards securing long term funding for researcher access of stations, knowledge exchange between stations, and the improvement and harmonisation of equipment, data collection and data sharing.

2.3. Wildfire: Definition of Shared Arctic Variables

Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SiOS); Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI)

2.3.1. Background

Shared Arctic Variables represent measurable phenomena critical to multiple Arctic rights holders and stakeholders, ensuring coordinated, standardised observations aligned with Indigenous, local, regional and global priorities.

The concept of SAVs is preferred by the AOS Indigenous Food Security Working Group as a more inclusive and useful framework, especially in comparison to the earlier concept of Essential Arctic Variables (EAVs). For example, a SAV might address information needs expressed by Arctic communities, serve Arctic climate research interests and address variability of the local environment, while at the same time tie back to an Essential Variable in the context of a global climate observing system. Hence, SAVs are essentially key variables grouped under thematic areas, selected because they are relevant to Arctic communities and decision-makers, feasible to observe or monitor, and valuable for integrating scientific and local knowledge. While EAVs were originally specified in the European Commission's call text that Arctic PASSION responded to, the SAVs approach was ultimately found to better reflect the project's priorities and the broader perspectives of its stakeholders.

Work on the SAV definitions for wildfire is undertaken in parallel in Finland and North America. Wildfire behaviour and effects vary across different regions of the Arctic. In some areas, wildfires are more frequent, intense and expansive, while in others they tend to be smaller and easier to extinguish. In addition, the causes of wildfires may differ depending on local conditions. In Finland most are human-caused fires and only about 13% of wildfires are lightning-ignited.

2.3.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

As part of Arctic PASSION, and shared process between WP1 and WP6, a SAV for Wildfire called Ignition Identification was defined (D1.2; D6.3). The Finnish National Wildfire project (Arctic Wildfire Preparedness) supported and contributed to this work. This Wildfire SAV consists of three elements: human activities, ignition detection and fire prone terrain. Examples of related data include mapped routes in Northern Finland, active fires and their progression from Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) satellites, and the Normalized Difference Moisture Index derived from interpreted Sentinel-2 (S2) satellite data.

Ignition identification helps reduce false alarms and improves the application of fire and smoke propagation predictions by rescue service. There is potential for sharing ignition related data and information about fire prone areas. The process also improves the information on vegetation and soil moisture. Local observations remain essential, at least until machine learning models or additional satellites resources become more widely available.

During the Finnish Wildfire SAV work, the Wildfire Expert Panel Fennoscandia was initiated. This panel engaged local, regional and global organisations including Indigenous Sámi representatives (e.g. reindeer herders), the Lapland Rescue Service, the Finnish Forest Center, Regional Administration, and researchers. In its initial phases, the focus was to identify key needs with broad benefits across Indigenous, regional and global levels.

Following the International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IDA, 2017), a Value Tree for the Wildfire Service was developed to assess societal benefits and to identify specific SAVs for the panel to address. Locally relevant variables were identified, particularly those related to ignition

(e.g. fire use, lighting, satellite hotspot observations) and fire prone areas (e.g. fuel availability, soil moisture, fire weather indices, microclimate modelling, protection needs).

In the third phase, the panel worked to jointly define requirements for the proposed SAVs by translating identified needs into concrete specifications and determining the necessary information and data, including what is already available. As part of the implementation phase, a mobile phone application will be developed to collect terrain moisture observations from individuals walking in nature, contributing to wildfire-related moisture monitoring.

The engagement of Finnish Sámi communities was successful as there were existing networks in place to facilitate collaboration and rapid progress. In North America, the work is still in its early stages, but progress was made as leadership roles were clarified, and network and workshop activity increased.

2.3.3. Ways forward

The goal of the Wildfire Expert Panel Fennoscandia has been to implement the defined Wildfire SAV Ignition Identification first in Finland, followed by other Nordic Countries, and eventually in North America. Funding has been secured until April 2026 (D6.3). In addition to developing the local observation mobile app, networking activities to engage Nordic country partners in a Northern European demonstration of the Wildfire SAV will help prepare for the next phase of the ROADS process for Wildfire (Phase IV).

2.4. Wildfire: Web mapping service (Arctic Service *INFRA*)

Italian National Research Council, Institute of Polar Sciences (CNR-ISP)

2.4.1. Background

Ensuring the resilience of communities to the danger of forest fires requires improvements in societal ‘fire risk literacy’, that is, awareness of actual risks and understanding what constitutes an effective response in the event of an emergency. People’s perception of wildfire risk largely determines how they respond in the event of an emergency. It is therefore important to foster a culture of effective fire risk management, in which the ecological role of fire is clearly distinguished from the risk-prevention measures associated with potentially catastrophic wildfires.

Creating a smooth and constant flow of information and paying attention to which local scale is most relevant for the end-user, is critical to achieving this goal. Whether the information flow and functionalities are useful depends largely on the end user’s role and degree of training in fire management. Currently, there is a notable lack of information pathways aimed at non-professionals and community members. For many, simply knowing what data is available and where to find it remains a substantial obstacle. Among the challenges to be addressed in the Arctic are difficulties in accessing fast and reliable internet connections.

2.4.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Arctic PASSION has developed a web mapping service for wildfires to facilitate the access to relevant information from diverse sources and products. Focusing on a local scale, the *INFRA* wildfire mapping service provides the possibility to generate and distribute wildfire-related alerts and information products tailored to non-scientific end-users such as municipalities, Indigenous Peoples, and local communities. The service currently covers Sakha-Yakutia, Fennoscandia and Alaska.

This approach has not only strengthened the flow and usefulness of information but also reduced the distance between the data source and the end-user, creating new opportunities to integrate local knowledge and perspectives. In this respect, the two main modules of INFRA are particularly useful:

- INFRA-AEGIS: A web-GIS platform that presents, combines and integrates all the information layers produced by INFRA or collected from a range of other sources and services.
- INFRA-SENTRY: A platform for distributing wildfire-related alerts and information to users. Alerts can be easily managed and tailored to specific needs and are generated in accordance with the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) Standard.

The information layers include risk indexes, ignition risk level, active fires, meteorological conditions, damage assessment, infrastructures/points of interests (e.g. communities). High-resolution numerical weather prediction model forecasts can be incorporated to provide, currently, thirteen different meteorological information layers.

Taking advantage of this modularity, a multi-level implementation strategy has been implemented, aligning the use of INFRA to both the user interests/capacities and the resources users have at their disposal.

2.4.3. Ways forward

Details on INFRA and its functionalities, approaches and future developments, can be found in the deliverables of WP4 (D4.3, D4.12), the Work Package responsible for developing all Arctic Services. The focus here is on items related to observations:

The INFRA service increases the value and usefulness of observations and information collected by various actors at different levels. Its modular design, cloud-based implementation, and multi-level development make it easier to transform routine observations into practical products, such as risk indices. The service also creates opportunities to include local knowledge and information in the data flow to end users, particularly those without technical expertise.

So far, INFRA has primarily drawn information from the Global Wildfire Information Service (GWIS) platform. A key goal for CNR is to broaden the scope of data and observations used by the service, incorporating also information connected with the emissions arising from wildfires as provided by Copernicus Atmospheric services (CAM5). A further step will be to connect INFRA with the AURORAE service related to air quality [4.1]. Another goal is to fully realize the added value of the service by involving local communities and end users, who often hold the most current information, in improving documentation of its functionality and use. A third line of action is to actively implement the inclusion of local knowledge and information in the data flow itself, engaging local rights-holders who have the authority to collect and share this information.

2.5. Permafrost: Observing best practices

Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)

2.5.1. Background

Permafrost refers to ground that remains at or below 0 °C for at least two consecutive years, often persisting for millennia and reaching substantial depths. It occurs in cold regions of both hemispheres, including polar and high-altitude areas. Warming and thawing of permafrost can significantly affect ecosystems, hydrology, and landscape stability, with implications for both natural and human systems (Ward Jones et al., 2019; Liljedahl et al., 2016; Walvoord and Kurylyk, 2016).

As a subsurface thermal feature, permafrost is highly sensitive to climate change and has been designated an Essential Climate Variable (ECV) by the Global Climate Observing System (GCOS, 2016). Long-term trends in permafrost temperature serve as indicators of climate change (Biskaborn et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2022).

The Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P) is the main international program for permafrost monitoring (Streletskiy et al., 2021). Because permafrost is a subsurface phenomenon, its observation relies on in situ measurements. Key indicator variables, defined within the GCOS Implementation Plan (WMO, 2022), are used to track long-term changes and are implemented through GTN-P (Smith and Brown, 2009; Streletskiy et al., 2021). Standardised methods and strategic planning are essential for producing consistent and comparable records over time (Noetzli et al., 2021).

2.5.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

The development of permafrost best practice guidelines, published as part of WMO Guide No. 8, was a key achievement within the work on the Permafrost Arctic Service (ALEX)[2.6], and the broader Arctic PASSION project. These guidelines support global standardisation of permafrost measurements and extend beyond the Arctic to include Antarctica and the Third Pole, encompassing the Tibetan Plateau and surrounding high mountain areas.

Permafrost data are collected worldwide through the GTN-P network and stored in its centralized database. However, the loss of access to Russian permafrost data represents a major setback for the scientific community, limiting the ability to assess global permafrost temperature trends under climate change.

While satellite data and modelling approaches can help mitigate this gap, they rely on in situ measurements for calibration and validation and cannot fully replace ground-based observations. These emerging technologies are still under development and thus not included in the first edition of the guidelines.

2.5.3. Ways forward

The inclusion of the best practices in WMO Guide No. 8 is expected to ensure their long-term impact and adoption. This guide will increase global standardisation of permafrost observations and access to harmonised data to advance necessary scientific research, including supporting the implementation of other WMO flagship initiatives such as the Global Greenhouse Gas Watch (G3W). Scientists from the GTN-P network were central in the development of the Permafrost Best Practices and the GTN-P community is an important group for distributing the document.

2.6. Permafrost: Land surface change (Arctic Service ALEX)

Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)

2.6.1. Background

Permafrost warming poses a significant threat to the Arctic region and has far-reaching global consequences. Thawing permafrost contributes to the erosion of coasts and riverbanks (Lantuit et al., 2013; Mann et al., 2022), causes land surface subsidence through thermokarst processes (Grosse et al., 2013), and undermines the integrity of infrastructure (Hjort et al., 2022) among other impacts. These permafrost-related changes affect the livelihoods, culture, and identities of Indigenous Peoples and other Arctic residents (Hovelsrud et al., 2011).

Given the rapid landscape changes driven by permafrost thaw, there is a growing demand for a service providing advanced information on recent or ongoing thaw, erosion, and associated risks. There is also a pressing need for support in planning mitigation strategies to address the impacts of permafrost degradation. A service offering accessible and user-friendly tools for permafrost-affected communities would be highly valuable in this process.

Permafrost disturbances can be detected using remote sensing analysis and mapped at high spatial resolution over large regions to quantify landscape change, hydrological dynamics, and permafrost vulnerability. Earlier work carried out through the ERC PETA-CARB, ESA CCI Permafrost, and NSF Permafrost Discovery Gateway projects laid the groundwork for a pan-Arctic time series dataset, which captures permafrost landscape change at 30-meters resolution over a twenty-year period using Landsat TM, ETM+, and OLI imagery (see Nitze and Grosse, 2016; Nitze et al., 2025).

2.6.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Building on the pan-Arctic dataset, Arctic PASSION served to document disturbance trends associated with abrupt permafrost degradation, aiming to enhance information distribution for better management, increased safety, and more targeted local responses. The change algorithm and processing pipeline were refined to provide more robust results in areas where data sources are disrupted, and the time series dataset has been updated to reflect more recent changes.

The main achievement within Arctic PASSION was, however, the development and successful launch of the Arctic Landscape EXplorer (ALEX), within Work Package 4. The new portal provides interactive maps of recent information on land surface changes, hot spots of disturbance, and potential areas of active permafrost thaw and erosion. The scientific findings from the large remote sensing dataset are made easily accessible through this tailored web-based portal. While the tool is actively used in scientific contexts, it is specifically designed for non-scientific audiences, including Indigenous community members, planners, landowners, public service staff, and the general public. Valuable feedback gathered during multiple research visits to Canada and Alaska was incorporated into the ongoing development of the tool. A recent Value Change Analysis (VCA) highlights the societal and economic importance of accurate information on Arctic permafrost conditions, as well as the benefits of using the ALEX tool to support mitigation efforts.

2.6.3. Ways forward

Establishing a system to detect land surface changes caused by permafrost degradation has been a key contribution to building a tailored, coherent, and integrated Arctic observing system. The Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research will continue to update and refine the change dataset behind the ALEX tool, while also maintaining the tool itself, expanding selected functionalities, and incorporating user feedback in future development.

2.7. Permafrost: Definition of Shared Arctic Variables

Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SiOS); Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI)

2.7.1. Background

Permafrost degradation affects infrastructure, ecosystem stability, resource management, and cultural practices. It also plays a critical role in climate feedback through the release of greenhouse gases. The expected changes in permafrost conditions are already having, and will continue to have, major consequences for both Arctic communities and the natural environment. The societal relevance of this work is therefore significant.

The Permafrost Expert Panel has two regional foci: Tuktoyaktuk in the Northwest Territories, Canada, and the Norwegian Archipelago in Svalbard. The panel comprises Indigenous Peoples, the communities of Tuktoyaktuk in Northwest Territories, Canada, and Longyearbyen, Svalbard as well as engineers, natural scientists, medical scientists, and social scientists [2.3] [3.5].

Using the International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IDA, 2017) and other evaluation tools, the panel has assessed the societal benefits of its work and aims to deliver outcomes that support both local adaptation strategies and broader scientific goals.

2.7.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Arctic PASSION supported the work to identify SAVs for Permafrost. The definition process progressed to the end of the second phase of the ROADS-defined process (Starkweather, 2021), with two SAVs proposed by the Permafrost Expert Panel: Permafrost temperature and Active layer thickness. These two properties have also been defined as Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) by the Global Climate Observing Systems (GCOS). The SAVs are expanding the scope on both observational capacities and stakeholder needs, incorporating the perspectives from Indigenous Peoples, medical sciences and social sciences. Monitoring these properties enables both the tracking of ongoing changes in the terrain, and development of awareness around expected future changes including risks to existing structures and considerations for future infrastructure development. A third SAV was identified related to changes in wellbeing resulting from changes in the permafrost and other parts of the environment. This SAV is not as well-defined as the other two at this point, but self-perceived human health-related indicators are proposed to be considered further.

One key asset identified while developing these SAVs is the opportunity for better information exchange between the different communities and stakeholders. It has become clear that the local actors rarely know of all the different monitoring efforts being carried out on the permafrost theme by authorities and scientists. Better awareness is expected to help drive collaboration and inclusion.

Early involvement of Indigenous Peoples is essential, and dedicated funding is needed to support their participation in the Expert Panel. Building relationships with previously uninvolved communities and stakeholders requires time and repeated engagement. However, convening diverse disciplines around a shared theme enables joint identification of current needs, exploration of relevant observations, and consideration of how communities can contribute to data collection while benefiting from the resulting services. Organizing panel activities and meeting opportunities with participants from across the Arctic (Alaska, Europe and Asia) is challenging, both with respect to high travels costs for in-person meetings, and with respect to finding commonly suitable hours for online meetings. The approach of regional Expert Panels is logistically more feasible.

2.7.3. Ways forward

The SAV development work aims to provide direct guidelines and tools for local communities seeking advice and inspiration on how to address permafrost changes. For permafrost it is important that the Expert Panel's work continues beyond Arctic PASSION, and participants have discussed how to achieve this (D6.3). Support is currently being sought to carry forward further work on the permafrost SAVs. The Arctic Circle Assembly in Reykjavik serves as an important venue for gathering feedback from the ROADS Advisory Panel to the Phase II documents and for outlining the next phase, including concrete next steps for the Expert Panel. The first draft of the Phase III document is expected to be ready by the end of Arctic PASSION.

2.8. Lake Ice Arctic Service

Finnish Environment Institute (FEI/Syke)

2.8.1. Background

The Arctic faces significant challenges due to climate change. As the lake ice cover period shortens, it has become essential to develop a comprehensive observing system to meet the growing need for timely and accurate information on ice conditions. Communities and industries operating in the Arctic, especially those relying on ice for transportation and livelihood, have been calling for an integrated approach to lake ice data. This information must be easily accessible and updated frequently, as ice conditions can change rapidly. Monitoring lake ice is crucial not only for safety but also for early adaptation to environmental changes driven by rising temperatures. The sensitivity of lake ice to temperature fluctuations and long-term trends underscores the importance of monitoring for both climate adaptation and practical decision-making in the Arctic.

Although ice data is already available from several Earth Observation (EO) products, this information is scattered across different services, often making it difficult to use it in a coherent way. Local communities have resorted to informal solutions, such as WhatsApp groups, to share observations on ice conditions. However, these methods are unsystematic, lack verification, and are not integrated into formal decision-making processes. There has been a clear demand for a more unified and accessible system that can consolidate these fragmented data sources and provide actionable insights.

2.8.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

The Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety established during Arctic PASSION addresses this gap by integrating EO-derived data, in situ measurements from governmental networks, and community-based monitoring. These data are then visualized in an easily understandable format, providing a comprehensive view of lake ice conditions. One of the service's innovative features is the ability for users to make observations based on satellite images, such as identification of cracks in the ice cover, and report these through the service. This contributes to a growing database of local knowledge and observations that are essential for safety and adaptation.

Photo (Esa Nikunen, Syke's Image bank): Heading out across the frozen lake to set winter nets – a traditional Arctic fishing practice.

The Lake Ice Service relies on a combination of observations and technical solutions to provide accurate and timely information on lake ice conditions (Figure 2). Key data sources include:

Optical Satellite Imagery: Provides high and moderate-resolution true colour images as well as Copernicus lake-ice extent data. These images are used to track lake ice extent and the changes in ice coverage but are limited by cloud cover and the polar night.

SAR Imagery: Sentinel-1 Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) data is used to complement optical data by penetrating cloud cover and providing observations during the polar night, which is critical in Arctic regions.

Water Temperature Maps: These maps provide insights into the thermal dynamics of lakes and help predict when ice formation may occur.

On-site Observations: Data from governmental Ice Thickness Stations in Finland provide continuous, high-precision measurements of ice thickness, which is a crucial factor in assessing ice stability and safety.

Community-based Monitoring: Observations from residents, including from Indigenous communities, offer real-time, localized insights that complement satellite data, making the service more responsive and contextually relevant.

All data sources were integrated into the service during the project. New observation routines were incorporated to enhance the service's reliability and coverage. One significant addition was the integration of community-based observations. This allowed for real-time reporting of ice conditions directly from the field, such as identifying cracks in the ice, which satellite data alone might miss. Additionally, the development of the Highlighting Interesting Phenomena (HISP) tool enabled users to report unusual ice conditions directly through satellite images, and thereby plan routes, alert others, and contribute to a growing database of local knowledge.

Figure 2. Screen capture of the Lake Ice Service representing northern Fennoscandia on 22 May 2024. Copernicus Continental Europe Lake Ice Extent data at front and Sentinel2/MSI, and Sentinel-3/OLCI true colour images at background. The orange circles represent on-site ice thickness observations and by clicking one of them, the user gets information that appears in the popup window on the map.

Some challenges and gaps were identified during the process:

- SAR imagery, while essential for coverage during the polar night, can be challenging to interpret, particularly regarding ice thickness and stability. There is a need for further development in SAR data interpretation to improve its accessibility and usability for non-expert users.
- While the network of Ice Thickness Stations in Finland provides valuable data, the geographical coverage could be expanded to include more remote areas and smaller lakes that are not currently monitored in detail.

2.8.3. Ways forward

For the future, it is essential to ensure the sustainability of the observations upon which the Lake Ice Service depends. Expanding both satellite and in situ observation networks, particularly in remote and poorly monitored areas, will enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the service. Furthermore, incorporating Copernicus Higher-Resolution Water Snow Ice (HR-WSI) data, expected to be available by 2026, will offer more detailed insights into smaller water bodies and enable more effective monitoring during the polar night, which is crucial for the Arctic.

The Lake Ice Service will continue operating within Syke's Tarkka platform, ensuring the long-term availability of both near-real-time and historical lake ice information. The service will also continue to evolve in close collaboration with users to better meet their needs and support decision-making. Continued collaboration with Indigenous and other Arctic communities will be important for keeping the service relevant and useful. The Lake Ice Service should be integrated more thoroughly into a broader Arctic observing system which includes both natural and socio-economic data, facilitating better decision-making across sectors. Linking ice data with weather, hydrology, and transportation systems could help create a more comprehensive and resilient observing system.

2.9. Land ice

University of Bristol (UBristol)

2.9.1. Background /Previous recommendations and needs

One of the consequences of the intensive Arctic warming is increasing loss of land ice. Changes in Arctic land ice challenge the sustainability of ecosystems and coastal communities within and beyond the Arctic. Between 2003 and 2019, the Greenland Ice Sheet (GrIS) lost about twice as much mass as the Antarctic Ice Sheet. Glaciers and ice caps (GICs) in Alaska, the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Iceland, Svalbard, and the Russian Arctic Islands – and peripheral GICs in Greenland were responsible for approximately 71% of the global GIC mass loss during the same period. As a result, Arctic land ice loss is currently a major contributor to global sea level rise, which has profound and long-lasting impacts on the Earth system and globally on coastal communities.

Arctic land ice loses mass through two processes: decreasing surface mass balance and increasing solid ice discharge. The negative surface mass balance can result in growing liquid meltwater discharge into the Arctic seas. The meltwater discharge at the ice-ocean interface of marine-terminating glaciers can also exert feedback mechanisms on solid ice discharge by influencing calving and ice dynamics. In the meantime, glacier calving can increase solid ice discharge by accelerating the ice flow and thinning the glacier ice.

There is a need for an improved satellite observing system for Arctic land ice to serve operational to long-term planning and policy needs. Specifically, this means developing a comprehensive monitoring concept for Arctic land ice, utilizing data from the Copernicus programme and Sentinel satellite series

funded by the EC, accompanied by third-party science missions supported by NASA, DLR, CNES and other national space agencies.

2.9.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Our observational activities in Arctic PASSION have focused on monitoring surface meltwater production and calving front change dynamics by utilizing different Earth Observation datasets and climate model outputs. GIC mass balance monitoring programmes have been supported by ESA and NASA, although continuity is not guaranteed.

Existing data products of meltwater production along Arctic coastlines often lack the detail needed in space and time as they rely on regional climate model (RCM) outputs. To improve this, a new scalable method was developed to downscale RCM data. This approach was applied to the MAR model, to create a high-resolution (250 m, daily) pan-Arctic discharge dataset for the period of 1950-2022. The dataset includes regions like the Canadian Arctic Archipelago, Greenland, Iceland, Svalbard, and the Russian Arctic Islands.

By combining RCM outputs with high-resolution Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), the method generates detailed coastal meltwater estimates and separates the sources such as tundra, ice surfaces, and ice below the snowline. Compared to earlier runoff products, this dataset captures narrow, low-lying glaciers thanks to its finer resolution. The approach is well suited for operational use and could be offered as a near real-time (NRT) service using MAR forecast data, similar to the GrIS system run by the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland.

Frontal ablation is a key component of the total mass balance of marine-terminating glaciers, which includes iceberg calving and frontal melting. This process can be quantified by tracking the glacier calving front using satellite images. The existing calving front datasets are limited to either a small sample of glaciers or to low temporal resolutions in calving front observations. Calving front mapping of glaciers has primarily relied on manual delineation from optical satellite imagery. In the meantime, the growing availability of extensive satellite datasets imposes a capacity challenge for manual delineation. This was addressed by using a novel deep learning model Charting Outlines by Recurrent Adaptation (COBRA) that can map calving fronts automatically at large spatial scales from multisource satellite images, including Landsat, Terra-ASTER, Sentinel-2 optical images, and Sentinel-1 SAR images. We applied this deep learning framework to 149 marine-terminating glaciers in Svalbard, one of the fastest-warming places on Earth, and produced a new high-resolution calving front dataset containing nearly 125,000 glacier calving front traces over the period of 1985-2023. The data pipeline for this mapping also has the potential for operationalisation providing NRT calving fronts as well as spatially differentiated calving fluxes.

The GrIS is a leading contributor to global sea level rise, and it has been losing significant mass, albeit with large interannual variations. The current remote sensing methods for measuring the GrIS mass balance have difficulty in separating mass changes caused by surface mass balance loss or dynamical mass loss, making interpretation of the driving mechanism difficult. To solve this problem, a Bayesian hierarchical model (BHM) framework was used to incorporate multiple satellite and in situ datasets, aiming to improve the mass balance estimates with a finer temporal resolution between 2002 and 2023 and to partition the contribution between surface processes and ice dynamics. The BHM can simultaneously assimilate the diverse observations with different spatio-temporal resolutions and reduce the uncertainties and assumptions when generating the reconciled mass balance.

2.9.3. Ways forward

Diverse high-resolution satellite observations and accurate regional climate model outputs are needed to establish a comprehensive and integrated Arctic land ice observing system. The EC Copernicus programme provides for some of the operational observational needs but not all. Current approaches are still reliant on non-operational science-focused missions such as the ESA Earth Explorer missions and the joint NASA-DLR GRACE missions. Future observational activities, in general, lack redundancy and are therefore vulnerable to funding cycles and hardware failure. For this reason, multi-sensor and diverse approaches are desirable.

The hydrological routing and runoff integration procedure used in our meltwater discharge downscaling algorithm is highly simplified, assuming the surface meltwater is instantaneously transported to the coastline. A better understanding of this process can further reduce the uncertainties in the meltwater discharge dataset. This would require accurate surface meltwater observations, either from in situ measurements or from satellite observations, which can be used to constrain the regional climate model runoff simulations and to improve the modelling of runoff routing at the glacier surface.

Understanding the glacier calving mechanism has been a long-standing challenge in glaciology. The existing glacier calving laws are overly simplified due to a lack of high-resolution glacier calving front datasets over a large spatial scale. The unprecedented spatial coverage and temporal resolution offered by our Svalbard glacier calving front dataset represent a step forward in addressing this challenge. A holistic glacier calving front observing system relies on publicly available optical and SAR images from multiple satellite platforms, as well as advanced automated calving front mapping algorithms. This also applies to the BHM framework for addressing the GrIS mass balance, which requires multiple satellite observations for elevation changes or mass changes of the ice sheet, including altimetry, gravimetry, GPS observations, and regional climate model outputs as prior information.

Recommendations for intermediate goals (1-3 years):

- Develop a scalable AI-driven tool for near-real-time glacier calving front monitoring using satellite data publicly available from NASA, ESA and other space agencies. Commercial satellite imagery does exist but would be prohibitively expensive for operational applications. This development aligns with the initiatives like the ESA AI4EO program and the NASA Earth System Observatory.
- Develop a comprehensive meltwater discharge in situ observation network and high-resolution modelling framework for Arctic glaciers and ice caps. This aligns with current EU-funded projects, like LIQUIDICE.
- Develop a collaborative framework for data harmonisation for Arctic glaciers and ice sheets integrating national and international initiatives.

Recommendations for long-term goals (5+ years):

- Build an integrated digital twin for Arctic land ice that combines Earth Observation data, numerical models, and Artificial Intelligence. This aligns with the EU Destination Earth and the ESA DTE initiatives.

3. Ocean and Sea ice

In recent decades variability in sea ice extent, concentration and absence of sea ice over longer periods and the loss of multi-year ice has characterized the Arctic Ocean and adjacent seas. The effects of these changes have influenced all aspects of life. The decline in multi-year ice and year-to-year changes in seasonal sea ice cover create risks, challenges and opportunities that affect all Arctic communities, pan-Arctic sectors, and global actors alike; therefore, continued, coordinated observation is crucial to understand the long-term trajectory and plan for and mitigate impacts.

Loss of sea ice also has global consequences, affecting biodiversity across a large portion of the planet, influencing the decision making of multinational and national corporations around transport, fisheries and development in the Arctic, and climate impacts for areas far removed.

In the marine realm, Arctic PASSION prioritized the expansion of in situ long-term observations, including new deep-ocean moorings in the central Arctic Ocean and enhancing coordination of drifting sea ice buoys in the European sector of the Arctic Ocean. Moorings were placed at new strategic locations [3.1], and several annual deployments of various drifting sea-ice buoys were carried out [3.2]. Within the scope of sea-ice buoys, considerable progress was made in harmonizing data processing for snow and ice thickness data from drifting mass balance buoys in the central Arctic Ocean, improving data quality and comparability from such observatories.

Satellite observations remain essential for monitoring sea ice and upper-ocean conditions, offering broad spatial coverage and frequent updates. However, in the high Arctic, persistent sea ice cover, frequent cloudiness, low solar angles, and polar night conditions limit the effectiveness of many satellite sensors, particularly for under-ice and subsurface observations. These limitations underscore the importance of complementary in situ measurements to fill spatial and temporal gaps and to capture processes occurring beneath the surface. A comprehensive observation system therefore requires satellite observations and traditional ground-based (in situ) observations to be effectively integrated. For this integration to be successful, onsite data must be of sufficient quality and in formats compatible with satellite data referencing. As part of WP1, three satellite datasets for sea-ice were co-developed and produced through collaboration with both internal and external partners and projects [3.3].

Within the scope of changing sea ice conditions, historical patterns of ship activity and risk were assessed to understand trends and needs in Arctic ship operations. A new shipping service was developed in WP4 applying the IMO POLARIS forecast methodology, based on sea ice forecasts by operational sea ice models [3.4] from WP1.

Arctic PASSION contributed to the SAON ROADS process for identification and implementation of Shared Arctic Variables (SAVs) [2.3][2.7]. For Sea Ice SAVs [3.5], the work progressed through the establishment of a Sea Ice Expert Panel. The purpose of this panel is to improve the coordination and relevance of sea ice observation in the Baffin Bay region while prioritizing societal benefit in the SAV identification and selection process.

The support from Arctic PASSION led to the establishment of the Atlantic-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory (A-DBO), as part of a suite of interdisciplinary marine observing networks across the Arctic Ocean tracking the impact of changing environmental drivers on the Arctic marine ecosystems [3.6]. WP1 also supported the development and expansion of community-based monitoring (CBM) in Qaanaaq, Greenland, and surrounding communities both through increased dialogue with the communities about their requests and needs from science, and through joint development of the practical deployment methods for handling scientific instrumentation [3.7].

3.1. Ocean: In situ observations

Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI), Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)

3.1.1. Background

Obtaining Arctic marine observations with sufficient temporal and spatial coverage, requires interdisciplinary measurements using a variety of platforms, sensors, and methods, spanning coastal areas, shelf seas, continental slopes, and deep ocean basins - from the sea surface (including sea ice and snow cover) to the seafloor.

Many institutions, funded through internal, national or competition-based sources, contribute to the Arctic observation efforts. To ensure cost efficiency and deliver consistent, user-friendly data and actionable knowledge, the entire data providing chain - from planning observation campaigns and long-term platform deployments, to processing and sharing data - must be well coordinated and harmonised.

3.1.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Through coordination and with partial funding from Arctic PASSION WP1, long-term deep-ocean moorings were deployed in the central Arctic Ocean (D1.7). The mooring locations were selected to capture emerging 'Atlantification' in the Nansen Basin and contrasting features of the Amundsen Basin, filling a geographical gap in the region (Figure 3). Core variables to target were identified and agreed upon and common sensor depths were identified for facilitating data comparison across these deep central Arctic Ocean basins. Two moorings in the western Nansen and Amundsen Basins (Nansen-22, Amundsen-22) were deployed in summer 2022 and serviced/re-deployed in 2024; at the time of writing having collected data over a three-year period. The ambition is to continue operating the two moorings for the foreseeable future, to establish long-term time series in key locations. For other locations, subject to 1–2-year mooring deployments during Arctic PASSION, the goal was to learn more about the environmental conditions at these locations before deciding on additional new long-term locations.

The new Arctic PASSION moorings were equipped with essential sensors and samplers, such as radiation and chl-*a* sensors and upward-looking sea ice thickness sonars, which all are typical components in similar mooring systems. Collecting key ECVs at the same locations throughout the seasonal cycle and over several years will provide a much better basis for understanding variability and change in the central Arctic Ocean. The new in situ datasets will be especially valuable for numerical ocean and sea ice reanalysis models and, hence, also contribute to the improvement of operational models. For more info about the deployments, instrumentation, and data availability, see report D1.7.

The inflow and outflow exchanges of the Arctic Ocean are reasonably well covered through long-term multi-institution monitoring programmes at the key gateways; Fram Strait and the Barents Sea opening, the Bering Strait area, and Davis Strait/Baffin Bay. Other parts of the interior Arctic Ocean have also been subject to dedicated continuous observations, e.g. the NABOS (UAF-IARC) and K-AWARE (KOPRI) programmes north of the Siberian shelf seas, multi-year moorings in the Chukchi Sea within ArCS I, II and now III (NIPR, JAMSTEC and others), and the US/Canadian Beaufort Gyre observing system (BGOS; WHOI, YALE, UW, DFO-IOS and others). In addition to filling geographical gaps in the Atlantic-influenced part of the Arctic Ocean, the Arctic PASSION mooring deployments are

Figure 3. Map showing the locations of NPI and AWI moorings deployed within Arctic PASSION 2022-2024. The coloured arrows show the main pathways of warm Atlantic water (red shades) and the cold polar waters (blue shades).

aligned with the site selection and instrumentation for the ongoing EU-funded High Arctic Ocean Observing System project (HiAOOS), which also strengthens environmental observations in the Nansen and Amundsen Basins.

Although progress has been made with respect to coordination of field campaigns, harmonisation of procedures and prioritizing of key variables, the Arctic Ocean is still severely under-observed. Key interfaces like land-coast and sea ice-upper ocean and regional hotspots of rapid change should be covered by continuous, long-term, inter-disciplinary monitoring programmes.

3.1.3. Ways forward

Coordination of observational activities with ice-capable research vessels in the Arctic is difficult. Different institutions have different planning horizons and different priorities regarding long-term monitoring, emerging research topics, and under-studied regions. During the second half of Arctic PASSION, annual meetings between chief scientists of campaigns to the central Arctic Ocean were held, with coordination also from the HiAOOS project, to identify synergies and plan mutually beneficial collaboration. In the future this should be a larger annual venue where also longer-term cruise plans are discussed to ensure optimal use of resources, ideally even before plans are submitted to funding agencies. The pan-Arctic DBO network [3.6] is a long-term network comprising many of the key institutions conducting science expeditions in the high Arctic, and this network could take responsibility for providing such an annual venue. Given that ocean moorings and drifting sea ice platforms are deployed and serviced by research vessels, planning of such operations could also be coordinated in concert with cruise information and planning meetings.

Locations, sensor selection and design of long-term ocean moorings must be known for planning the design and deployment of drifting sea ice platforms such that the two types of instrumentation together provide the best possible coverage of key variables in the water column – including the under-ice layer into which moorings normally do not extend to capture due to the risk of equipment

loss from deep sea ice keels. We recommend holding open annual meetings among those operating Arctic Ocean scientific campaigns, moorings, and sea ice platforms. Ideally, these meetings should include multi-year planning horizons to allow new proposals to align with existing programmes and schedules.

The shortfall of sustained, international and coordinated funding for in situ observations in the central Arctic Ocean combined with the high operational costs makes it difficult to establish comprehensive long-term monitoring programmes. From time to time, voluntary coordination efforts among the key actors improve the efficiency and ‘value for money’ but do not solve the fundamental problem which is the absence of sustained funding schemes. This issue cannot be addressed only by the observing community but must also be raised to the appropriate entities by users of such observational data.

3.2. Sea ice: In situ observations

Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research (AWI), Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI)

3.2.1. Background

Drifting sea-ice buoys are used to track the spatial and temporal evolution of the sea ice and its snow cover. They are deployed during expeditions and left behind to drift with the sea ice. They report their measurements through satellite communication in near real-time. Depending on the suite of sensors deployed, these drifting sensor platforms can allow monitoring of atmosphere, snow, sea ice, and ocean parameters when manned observations are not possible.

Such buoys come in different forms and levels of complexity. The simplest versions contain only GPS and temperature loggers to track the drift of the ice pack. More complex buoys also report physical properties of snow, sea ice, and ocean. Most sea ice buoys comprise a string of thermistors (temperature sensors) that capture the temporal evolution of temperature through the snow cover and sea ice, and into the underlying water mass. This allows for identification of the snow-sea ice interface and the snow-water interface, as well as capturing episodes of water intrusion and subsequent freezing at the snow-sea ice interface. Even more advanced drifting platforms comprise sensors measuring properties of the upper part of the water column, either at fixed depths on strings or in profiling units.

Data from sea ice buoys were also collected from fast ice in NW Greenland, of which the main parts are recorded in the vicinity of the DMI field facilities in Qaanaaq (NW Greenland), hereafter Qaanaaq Winter Observatory (QWO). This data set includes simultaneous data from Automatic Weather Stations (AWS) and Ice Mass Balance (IMB) buoys. The QWO data focus on surface temperature, but the data set also comprises several other related parameters, like air temperature and snow/ice interface temperature and snow albedo. This data set has so far been recorded over 12 years (2014-2025).

3.2.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

As part of Arctic PASSION, several drifting sea ice buoys or platforms with different combinations of instruments were deployed in the central Arctic Ocean:

Sea-ice mass balance buoys: These sea ice buoys comprise a string of thermistors (temperature sensors) that capture the temporal evolution of temperature through the air, snow, and sea ice, and into the underlying water mass. In Arctic PASSION we used thermistor string buoys with active heating cycles (SIMBA; Jackson et al., 2013). Data analysis allows the identification of the snow-sea ice and the

snow-water interfaces, and thus snow and sea ice thickness over time. In addition, they capture internal snow and sea ice properties, e.g. episodes of water intrusion and subsequent freezing at the snow-sea ice interface. An overview of deployments 2022-2024 is shown in Figure 4.

Snow buoys: These sea ice buoys are designed to measure snow depth and air temperature on sea ice. They are deployed on sea ice and have a mast that holds sensors to measure snow accumulation and ablation. They are often co-deployed with SIMBA buoys to support snow observations.

IAOOS platforms: Ice-tethered profilers which collect data from the upper ocean below drifting sea ice, usually deployed together with ice mass balance buoys.

In Arctic PASSION, new sensor combinations to reduce observational gaps were tested and proven successful. One suite comprised atmospheric sensors, strings with under-ice sensors measuring photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), and an active-acoustic echosounder for zooplankton and fish biomass estimates, in addition to SIMBA sea ice thickness buoys.

As of summer 2024, 43 SIMBA thermistor string buoys, 23 snow buoys, and five IAOOS profilers were deployed with funding contributions from Arctic PASSION. Additional sea ice (9) and snow buoys (3) were deployed in 2025 by AWI and NPI – without direct funding from Arctic PASSION but following planning and deployment procedures from the project. In addition, SIMBAs were repeatedly deployed over several consecutive winters in Qaanaaq.

Work with IMB buoys and data in Arctic PASSION showed the importance of use of consistent protocols for IMB deployments, and the need to account for time that must be spent for QA/QC of buoy data during processing and analysis. Most of these instruments, in particular thermistor string buoys, do not measure sea ice and snow thicknesses as such, but sea ice temperature and thermal proxies, which then need to be converted into mass balance terms.

Figure 4. Drift tracks of thermistor string buoys deployed during Arctic PASSION (Status 31 Dec 2024). Deployments from different expeditions are grouped by colour for each year. The background shows the sea ice concentration of September 2012, at the summer minimum extent.

This adds a major challenge to the measurements and their analyses, as there is no universally agreed processing and conversion protocol. During Arctic PASSION progress was made in establishing common data processing protocols to retrieve sea ice mass balance time series. Similar challenges exist for many other parameters which may only be derived indirectly; additional calibration and validation measurements are needed, and the improvement of existing algorithms will increase the reliability of the observations.

The QWO data are mainly used as reference for satellite-based ice surface temperature retrievals that are essential to fill the observational gaps in polar regions. The recording of ice buoy data, simultaneous with AWS data, enables pre and post deployment performance evaluation of the ice buoys, which is a crucial aspect of Fiducial Reference Measurements (FRM). FRMs provide the desired high-quality observations needed for proper evaluation of satellite Ice Surface Temperature (IST). The value and concepts of FRM in relation to end-to-end calibration of satellite products is explained in more detail in (D1.6).

3.2.3. Ways forward

To fill existing observation gaps in time and space, improved spatial coverage with autonomous devices for snow and sea ice observations and the ability to collect more observations during winter are needed. The international community needs to commit to run these programmes over decades to build meaningful time series.

Regular international network meetings within the IMB community aid in sharing information on various systems and buoy setups, data processing and interpretation, available instrumentation and deployment strategies and opportunities. Such networking could help to establish a common information and planning tool (e.g. web page) for planned expeditions that accommodate deployments of autonomous systems.

Technical improvements and ways forward include accounting and arranging for additional ship time to test systems immediately after deployment on site, efficiently combining IMB deployments with deployments of other autonomous equipment, and development of recovery plans for deployed instrumentation. Recent developments in broadband satellite communications allow for new instruments that produce larger volumes of data (e.g. multibeam echosounders and broadband passive acoustic sensors) to be deployed from drifting sea ice platforms. With a growing number of costly instrument packages being deployed, their recovery becomes more important.

Merging in situ manned with un-manned/autonomous observations can be a step to improve time series measurements in the future. Stations requiring little maintenance can significantly elevate the data quality and reduce instrument failures. The opportunity to re-visit stations and add manned observations to autonomous time series is most valuable.

The performance of satellite-based IST retrievals is strongly dependent on high-quality ground reference data. The way forward is to significantly increase the number of high-quality sea ice buoys. Traditional sea ice buoys are often not suited for satellite data validation or as input to numerical weather prediction analysis. A cost efficient and easy-to-handle FRM compliant sea ice buoy system is needed to fill in the gaps between the advanced and complex ice buoy systems mentioned above. The Copernicus ice buoy development project TRUSTED, with EUMETSAT as the leading entity, will in the coming years test a new ice buoy design as a complementary buoy system to the existing high-end ice buoys. The TRUSTED buoy will also provide crucial real time access to surface temperature and snow/ice interface temperatures, which is important input to analysis fields in operational models. The development phase lasts until the end of 2027, and the buoy is expected to be ready for commercial distribution shortly thereafter.

Finally, future observational systems will need to realize a larger proportion integrated measurements of physical, biological and geochemical parameters compared to earlier setups, to improve understanding of how changes in these different system components relate to changes and impacts in the other components.

3.3. Sea Ice: Remote sensing activities

Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI)

3.3.1. Background

A comprehensive observation network also requires a system that integrates the satellite observation system with traditional ground-based observations, via thorough knowledge of the relationship between in situ point measurements and area-mean measurements from satellite data. This integration of satellite and ground observations is of particular importance in Polar areas, where ground-based observations are sparse, because of the challenging environment. To exploit the full value of ground observations as reference to satellite measurements, thorough knowledge of the full uncertainty budget for doing this is essential.

3.3.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Through interaction with both internal and external partners and projects, Arctic PASSION contributed to the development and production of three Arctic datasets. One data set is the sea ice in situ data set, described above [3.2].

The second dataset is a 43-year long global monthly mean ice surface temperature record for Polar regions (Dybkjær et al. 2025), jointly developed by Arctic PASSION WP1 and Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S Sea Ice TAC). The data set is based on Kolbe et al. (2025) and is a strong stand-alone data set useful for example for climate analysis, and a tool for model evaluation and tuning.

The third data set was produced in support of the pilot Arctic Service 6 [3.4] and is a reprocessed Risk Index Outcome (RIO) which is a critical component of the IMO developed POLARIS system. Based on ship ice class, sea ice type/stage of development and sea ice concentration RIO evaluates the operational risks for ships navigating in ice-infested waters and offers a quantifiable measure of risk to aid decision-making for safe navigation in Polar regions. The objective of this service was to test a RIO forecast product, where RIO “climatology” was used as supplementary tool for navigators to facilitate planning of Ship Routes, based on probability.

3.3.3. Ways forward

The RIO data are useful for planning of ship routing; however, they are presently not a standard tool for navigation in real time. An observation driven RIO index is currently based on time-averaged ice concentration products, e.g. daily mean products. These products are often outdated information for real time navigation, due to fast moving ice near the ice edge. A more applicable satellite-based RIO product must be based on ice information in near real time. A way forward is to produce RIO products based on level 2 satellite data, that is, geophysical variables derived from calibrated and geolocated satellite data. Such a RIO can be made available a few hours after satellite overpass and provide updated sea ice information for the ships that navigate in ice infested waters.

3.4. Sea ice: Shipping Safety (Arctic Service *POLARIS*)

British Antarctic Survey (BAS)

3.4.1. Background

The well documented changes to Arctic sea ice cover and thickness result in both opportunities and challenges for global shipping. Reduced sea ice has the potential to facilitate shorter shipping routes, such as the Northern Sea Route, reducing travel time and fuel costs. However, unpredictable sea ice conditions, even as sea ice is reduced, and extreme weather results in safety risks, uncertainty in travel times and potential impact on the environment in the event of an accident.

The adoption of the IMO Polar Code was a first step towards ensuring safe and sustainable shipping in the Arctic. It included a requirement for a methodology to determine the operational limitations in sea ice, to ensure that vessels are capable of navigating in the ice conditions anticipated for each operation. POLARIS was agreed upon by IMO as an integral tool of the Polar Code as it provides a methodology for assessing ice operational risk.

Ships already use multiple sources of sea ice and weather information to support situational awareness when navigating in the Arctic. These are reliant on sustained satellite Earth observation datasets, acquired over the Arctic throughout the year and made available in near-real-time to service providers and users.

The POLARIS methodology is an additional approach to assessing the risk to a ship, considering both the sea ice conditions and the ship's capabilities. POLARIS requires certain information about sea ice conditions which can be obtained from local ship observations or from ice charts published by the Arctic national ice centres. Access to ice charts is provided directly from each ice centre and collated into the Ice Logistics Portal supported by the International Ice Charting Working Group.

3.4.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

In addition to completing an assessment of the historical patterns of ship activity and risk to understand trends in Arctic ship operations, the Arctic PASSION shipping pilot service has developed and trialled a new forecast POLARIS methodology. This is based on sea ice information forecast by operational sea ice models, which typically include mean sea ice thickness and concentration variables. Models included in this development include the ECMWF S2S project, Copernicus Marine Data Store (CMDS) forecasts based on the TOPAZ coupled ocean-sea ice model, and the DMI coupled HYCOM ocean CICE ice model.

After demonstrations with ship-based users, it is concluded that POLARIS forecast information has potential application to support ship navigation, but mainly for longer term route planning and assessing ship ice classification requirements. Currently the information is too low resolution to support tactical ship navigation decisions.

3.4.3. Ways forward

To make POLARIS forecast information more useful in the future, several key improvements should be considered:

- Develop higher-resolution regional models to provide forecast sea ice information at the required spatial scale.
- Provide autonomous devices/buoys for sea ice observations to validate information derived from satellite Earth observation data.

- Coordinate the collection of POLARIS information from ships to support the validation and development of the POLARIS methodology, including error assessment of POLARIS forecasts from operational sea ice models.
- Follow the IMO plans to revise and improve the POLARIS methodology to address known limitations such as not including information about glacial ice or pressure ridging.

3.5. Sea Ice: Definition of Shared Arctic Variables

Arctic Institute of North America, University of Calgary (AINA), Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SiOS),

3.5.1. Background

Sea ice is of profound importance to Arctic Indigenous People and other Arctic residents. It serves as a critical platform for ecosystems, traditional travel routes, Indigenous subsistence activities and determining shipping lanes. However, rapid sea ice variability and decline over recent decades have had widespread impacts on both marine and terrestrial ecosystems and greatly altered circumstances, introducing risks, challenges, but also opportunities for Arctic communities and international stakeholders.

The decline of sea ice is hence having major social, environmental and economic consequences for the communities that rely on it for their livelihoods and food-security both through access to country food sources, individual travel and access to communities by re-supply vessels – particularly of issue in the Canadian Arctic. Specifically, safe travel on sea ice for people in northern communities is increasingly risky as both the sea-ice extent, thickness, and length of the sea ice season decreases. Opportunities created, such as improved re-supply leading to a reduction in the cost of store-bought food and other goods, can only be realized if shipping conditions are safe and predictable for operators which presents a real challenge in the context of ongoing variability and changes in sea ice conditions.

There is shared concern that current Arctic Observing System inputs are performing poorly and with little or no input regarding priorities from Arctic communities or Arctic Indigenous Peoples. This called for a Sea Ice Expert Panel to be formed, prioritizing societal benefit in the identification and selection of sea-ice relevant SAVs for observations.

The Baffin Bay region is fundamentally shaped by the seasonal waxing and waning of its sea ice cover. Its jurisdiction is shared by Inuit in Canada and Greenland, and by the governments of Canada, Greenland, and Denmark. The region, spanning from Ellesmere Island to Nunatsiavut, is notable for extensive political, economic, and cultural ties between Canadian and Greenlandic communities.

3.5.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

As a joint European/Canadian effort under the umbrella of Arctic PASSION and New Frontiers in Research Fund Canada, an Expert Panel on Sea Ice was formed. This group took a unique approach in its pilot effort, assembling a Steering Committee (SC). The SC has been responsible for initiating the process, conducting a review on the status of observing efforts in the Baffin Bay region, securing funding, and providing ongoing support to the panel. Expert Panel members were identified and nominated by one or more SC members and recruited to the panel. The intention was to bring together a diverse group of individuals that could contribute unique disciplinary expertise, lived experience and practical knowledge on sea ice. The SC also support panel members in navigating the SAON-ROADS process. The panel now consists of Inuit sea ice experts from Canada and Greenland, the operational ice services, and researchers with sea-ice relevant research on shipping, marine mammals, and policy.

The Expert Panel and the Steering Committee chose to focus on the Baffin Bay region – a region of common interest and focus of international co-management. The objective is to facilitate continued and coordinated monitoring of sea ice change in Baffin Bay and strengthen the existing observational networks in the region.

As the proposed International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework (IDA, 2017) was considered too prescriptive, the Expert Panel instead developed their own benefit assessment. This framework consists of four steps: 1) Identification of the societal benefit themes and sea ice variables; 2) Rating the relevance of the sea ice variables to each societal benefit theme; 3) Rating the efficacy of how each variable is measured; and 4) Rating the methodologies currently used to measure each variable. Only variables identified as relevant across all societal benefit themes were rated in Steps 3 and 4. This process is being documented in detail by the ROADS Advisory Panel, and recommendations about needed observations are anticipated in Phase IV (D6.3).

3.5.3. Ways forward

While the timeline for completion of the four-phase process is difficult to anticipate, there is both interest and sufficient funding to see the project continue beyond Phase IV to implementation. Funding for this project has successfully been secured through two main pathways: 1) request for project specific funding for the Sea Ice Expert Panel piloting the SAON ROADS process in the Baffin Bay region, and 2) request for Expert Panel funding as part of a broader research effort, where the panel is simply one tool amongst many and incorporated into a more comprehensive research scheme. Continuity in funding from the NordForsk SustainME project, combined with the remainder of the dedicated funding allocated under Arctic PASSION will allow the Sea Ice Expert Panel to meet in-person in Nuuk, during Greenland Science Week, 10-11 November 2025 to continue its work.

3.6. Distributed Biological Observatories

UiT The Arctic University of Norway (UiT), Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI)

3.6.1. Background

A major challenge in Arctic Ocean observations are various gaps in time and space, and in types of observations. Temporally we often lack seasonal coverage, and spatial gaps exist not only in the horizontal aspect, but also as poor coverage of ocean depths below the surface waters. An increasing number of automated oceanographic instrumentation and improved quality of increasingly diverse satellite-based observations help reduce such gaps.

Biological and ecological observations are particularly scarce. Sensor development has been slower than for e.g. physical oceanography, and the biologically important upper 50–100 meters of the water column pose high risks for instrument damage due to drifting sea ice. While remote sensing provides valuable information on sea ice and open water surface characteristics, it does not capture under-ice waters or vertical distributions. Annual ship-based surveys help fill this gap, but they are mostly conducted in summer when sea ice is reduced, leading to seasonal bias. Data not collected by moorings or remote sensing, therefore, remain limited in seasonal coverage.

The Distributed Biological Observatory (DBO) was initially developed to improve monitoring of ecosystem changes across the Pacific gateway to the Arctic (Moore and Grebmeier, 2018; Grebmeier et al., 2019; Figure 5). By coordinating ship-based observations at agreed key stations in known biological hotspots, the initiative increases the frequency of ecologically relevant measurements. It also strengthens collaboration among research communities, enhances observational capacity, and reduces fragmentation in data collection. As a result, there is now a broader understanding of

environmental and ecosystem changes along the Pacific Arctic inflow shelves, and their impacts on marine mammals, seabirds, and local communities. The DBO concept aligns well with earlier recommendations such as those from EU-PolarNet 2 (Lymer et al., 2024). These recommendations highlight the need to share observing infrastructures and coordinate activities, connections in time and space, and standardisation. They also highlight data, international collaboration and societal relevance (including education), as well as funding and societal benefits where long-term sustainability and dedicated action groups are suggested elements.

In 2016, a workshop supported by the IASC Marine Working Group, evaluated the need for a DBO in the Atlantic sector of the Arctic, and concluded that there was strong interest, and need, for enhanced coordinating capacity among relevant science communities.

3.6.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Arctic PASSION provided capacity and momentum to establish an Atlantic-Arctic DBO (A-DBO), aimed at improving coordination of existing observational activities in this region. Building on recommendations from the 2016 workshop, a set of transects was agreed upon with key stations representing ongoing long-term monitoring under various national and institutional responsibilities. To facilitate and strengthen collaboration among science communities working in the Atlantic-Arctic gateway, the focus was on creating meeting places to build the foundation for a continued A-DBO network. A landing page was established early as the main channel for information sharing, and a first set of shared tools for planning and reporting observational data was also developed (D1.3; Appendix 2).

During Arctic PASSION, bi-annual meetings were organised and the following successes achieved: 1) Establishing an organisational structure of the A-DBO that includes relevant institutions and science communities, 2) Formulating a vision of collaboration to optimize the observational capacity, with ambitions to improve harmonisation of methods and data, 3) Engaging a broader science community, including early-career professionals, to strengthen both disciplinary and interdisciplinary networks and support discussions on priority science questions and key features to monitor, 4) Promoting and contributing to the establishment of an expanded, pan-Arctic DBO network including the Pacific DBO, the A-DBO, and two complementary DBOs being established in the Siberian Seas and in the Baffin Bay/Davis Strait region, 5) Developing a vision and ambition for the pan-Arctic network of DBOs, and 6) Connecting to other relevant Arctic marine observational networks and initiatives such as the Synoptic Arctic Survey (SAS), the EuroGOOS Arctic ROOS, and the ongoing process to develop an Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance (ArORA).

3.6.3. Ways forward

With the rapid and multiple environmental changes taking place globally and regionally, some of which are propagating deep into the central Arctic Ocean, it is urgent to strengthen and optimize the observational capacity. There is great potential in a more synergetic use of existing structures and resources. Increased collaboration and harmonisation across programmes providing long-term time series and shorter-term, project-based activities will increase the value and reduce the fragmented nature of current observational efforts. This requires continuous attention and encouragement. At present, few incentives beyond the scientific reward exist.

There is a need for sustained and prioritized funding to facilitate collection of more and better observations including biologically relevant measurements across the Pan-Arctic domain. There is also a need for dedicated support to synthesise data and results targeting the larger Arctic region. Such synthesis activities will highlight the need for harmonised data practices and motivate the work on

data publications along the FAIR/CARE guidelines to increase the longevity and extended use of existing data.

Intermediate goals (1-3 years) recommendations:

- Support networks like the DBOs through sustainable funding to create meeting places and counteract fragmentation.
- Support early career professionals with travel funds, mobility grants and research projects to enhance scientific outcomes and foster international collaboration across existing time series datasets.
- Establish closer contact with rights holders and stakeholders to ensure inclusion of variables or samples that are particularly important for society and certain user groups.
- Encourage greater use and funding of ecologically relevant sensors and sensor development to expand and improve ecosystem observations.
- Promote data management practices that support identification, harvesting and harmonised use of data across storage platforms (e.g., the SIOS, SAON, PANGAEA databases).
- Strengthen collaboration with remote sensing and modelling communities to improve access to data needed for validation, evaluation and model input
- Support synthesizing research efforts using data across different observatories and observational approaches – providing valuable context for both planning and implementing the upcoming International Polar Year.

Figure 5. The pan-Arctic network of DBOs sampling locations overlaid on the Arctic Ocean bathymetry and a schematic of the main circulation pathways. Red/pink/green shades are used for inflowing waters from the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans and blue shades for outflowing surface polar waters. The indicated coastal communities are those where special efforts are made to co-develop coastal observation systems. See <https://arcticpassion.eu/adbo/> for more information on the A-DBO.

Long-term goals (5+ years) recommendations:

- Develop international agreements on joint observational contributions to pan-Arctic observatories.
- Prioritize long-term funding for nationally and institutionally driven collection of time series, encouraging national funding agencies and governments to support shared and collaborative responsibilities.
- Promote stronger links between research activities and existing observational networks and structures as these provide temporal and spatial context for new observations.
- Optimize observational strategies to detect changes and trends, including those relevant to societal needs and nature conservation.
- Harmonize observations across sites to capture site specific features and enable reliable comparisons.
- Continue advancing FAIR and CARE data handling practices to improve the usability and accessibility of collected data.

3.7. Coastal community-based monitoring (Arctic Service)

Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI), Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR)

3.7.1. Background

Indigenous communities in Northern Greenland rely on narwhal hunt and the narwhal is very sensitive to underwater noise. The decrease in sea ice due to global warming leads to thinner and less sea ice, which is of real safety and food security concerns to communities as they rely on sea ice for hunting and transport. Decreasing sea ice also leads to higher ambient noise levels from natural and anthropogenic sources, which is a major concern for families relying on hunting the sound sensitive narwhal.

Indigenous communities near the North Water Polynya (Pikialasorsuaq) are experiencing increasing tourism, research and exploration activities. Through the Pikialasorsuaq commission, the communities have expressed a need for more involvement and training in resource management and planning activities in the area including scientific monitoring.

Increasing ambient noise in relation to sea ice loss and increased shipping and other anthropogenic activities has been identified as a major concern in PAME and AMAP working groups.

3.7.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Arctic PASSION contributed to the development and expansion of community-based monitoring (CBM) in Qaanaaq and surrounding communities. This Arctic Service to monitor the marine climate and noisescape in coastal zones was co-created with the communities of Qaanaaq, Savissivik, Siorapaluk and Qerqertat in NW Greenland. The CBM activities include community meetings and dialogue forums, to identify and include local requests and science needs in monitoring. The scientific activities include monitoring of physical parameters such as snow and sea ice characteristics, sea water salinity and temperature, as well as ambient noise levels and monitoring marine mammals' sound with passive acoustic recorders. The latter activity has a special focus on narwhals because of the importance of narwhal to the local communities and their culture. Meetings and field activities are carried out 2-6 times per year.

The development of new deployment methods for advanced monitoring instrumentation through sea ice with dog sledges combines Indigenous knowledge and skills with scientific methods. This approach has worked out very well, and will continue to be applied in the future. Members of the communities will get regular training in the technical and practical tasks of operating the monitoring network of bottom-moored instrumentation.

Analysis of the collected data revealed that narwhals have a stronger link to the edge of the sea ice on their summer migrations than first expected. They are so closely linked that there may be unknown food sources associated to the melting sea ice edge. This new knowledge can lead to a better understanding of how disappearing sea ice affect marine ecology, narwhals and communities.

Community meetings and dialogues have helped to expose new scientific questions, such as finding ways to identify subpopulations of narwhals, both morphologically and genetically. This is a new project which has evolved from the CBM community meetings. Another example is a concern raised by community members over international scientists deploying active acoustic scientific instruments in narwhal hunting grounds. We have investigated this and found the sources of concern and presented it to the Greenland Government. The community concern raised during the dialogues has led to an increased awareness in the Greenland management bodies about using active acoustics for marine monitoring purposes in traditional hunting areas.

3.7.3. Ways forward

The now established CBM program in Qaanaaq will continue the basic monitoring with bottom moored loggers in a collaboration with the community.

The site has been designated as part of the Baffin Bay Distributed Biological Observatory (DBO) and will continue to evolve within the DBO community [3.6]. It serves as a strong example of how DBO sites can be relevant to local communities and aligned with their needs.

The pilot Arctic Service will in the future seek to develop into the Pikialasorsuami Nasiffik, a local driven science hub where researchers can contact the community to present plans, request local assistance and provide results from scientific projects. The local community can deliver community science needs and suggest involvement in activities.

A connection is currently being developed between the Qaanaaq CBM to the Grise Fjord CBM in Canada. This is meant to be a collaboration across the North Water Polynya, including monitoring sites in the polynya.

4. Atmosphere

For the atmosphere domain, Arctic PASSION supported the development of the Air Quality Forecast for Arctic Communities (AURORAE) Arctic service to release reliable short-term air pollution forecast as support to local communities, local authorities, policymakers and citizens and to align to the new European Air Quality Directive 2024/2881 [4.1]. The AURORAE service provides an easy-to use web interface that allows access to near-real time particular matter concentrations data and forecast for about a hundred air pollution monitoring stations in the European Arctic. Hence, added value is provided to air pollution observations, improving data accessibility and interoperability.

Arctic PASSION also contributed to making World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) Global Telecommunication System (GTS) real time exchange data available for non-GTS connected users [4.2]. The primary focus of the approach was to extract information from synoptic weather stations, radiosonde stations and ocean buoys.

Activities initiated within the EU H2020 Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium (ARICE) project were continued to take the opportunity offered by commercial passenger cruises for implementing cost-effective monitoring of surface radiation fluxes and cloud measurements over the Arctic Ocean [4.3].

4.1. Air Quality (Arctic Service *AURORAE*)

EC Joint Research Centre (JRC-ISPRA)

4.1.1. Background

For a long time, the atmosphere in the Arctic has been considered free from pollution until explorers in the 1950s observed the phenomenon of Arctic Haze, the accumulation of pollutants in the lowest part of the troposphere during winter and early spring. This phenomenon is driven by low temperatures during the cold Arctic winter trapping the atmospheric pollutants close to the Earth's surface. Particulate matter (PM) is an atmospheric pollutant which can be found in the Arctic and consists of a mixture of solids and liquid droplets containing several chemical species such as nitrate, sulphate, organic compounds, and many others. Nowadays, residential combustion for heating, shipping, oil extraction and metal smelting represent the main local PM sources in the extreme North. Due to the small size of the particulate, with 10 μm of equivalent diameter or less, called PM₁₀, the particles can enter the lungs through breathing, and exposure to high concentrations might cause respiratory problems, cardiovascular diseases and cancer. Considering the adverse health effects caused by PM₁₀, an accurate forecast of its concentrations is essential for pollution mitigation and emergency preparedness in Arctic villages and cities.

The forecast of PM₁₀ concentrations over Europe, including the Arctic, is performed by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), based on an ensemble of eleven state-of-the-art numerical air quality models. Nonetheless, the CAMS predictions have uncertainties, mainly related to errors in the input data such as initial state estimation, model parametrization, emissions, and model algorithms. Also, CAMS forecasted concentrations appear to agree less with in situ measurements of PM₁₀ in Northern Europe in comparison to other regions. In addition, CAMS air pollution forecasts are difficult to access by non-scientific and non-professional users.

4.1.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

As one of the Arctic PASSION Arctic Services developed in WP4 (D4.13; EC-JRC, 2024), the AURORAE air quality service was developed to provide reliable short-term air pollution forecasts tailored to the

needs of local communities, authorities, policymakers, and citizens in the European Arctic. The service also aligns with the new European Air Quality Directive 2024/2881 (EU, 2024), supporting policy planning and efforts to reduce population exposure to harmful pollutants. Producing accurate and accessible PM₁₀ forecasts for Northern European countries is therefore critical, particularly to empower Arctic communities and inform decisions on pollution reduction and prevention measures.

The AURORAE service provides an easy-to use web interface that allows access to near-real time PM₁₀ concentrations data and forecast for about a hundred air pollution monitoring stations. It is designed for a non-scientific audience, and users can easily visualize and download PM₁₀ at the selected stations through an interactive map. The service, in addition, aims at providing added value to air pollution observations, improving data accessibility and interoperability. This approach strengthens the effectiveness of the air pollution monitoring stations network and provides additional societal benefits to people living in the Arctic.

AURORAE is composed by three main modules:

- Data gathering module: it collects daily PM₁₀ concentrations from the European Environmental Agency (EEA) and Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) monitoring stations at one-hour resolution, CAMS weather meteorological fields forecast, and PM₁₀ CAMS forecast for North Europe as input to the Forecasting module.
- Forecasting module: consists of a Deep Learning model (Crossformer) that provides PM₁₀ concentration forecast for the upcoming 48 hours for each monitoring station.
- Online platform module (dashboard): the near real time PM₁₀ concentrations and the forecast are visualized on an interactive map in which all monitoring stations. The dashboard is the information access point for the users to visualize and download the PM₁₀ observation time series and forecasts for each station. In addition, the service releases a daily air pollution report with current PM₁₀ concentrations, forecasts for all monitoring stations, and pollution trends, available for free download.

During the development process we encountered the following challenges within the observational scope:

- Lack of sufficient spatial coverage of monitoring stations in the European Arctic - even though the service is tailored for all European Arctic communities the PM₁₀ forecast cannot be provided to all of them due to lack of data.
- Discontinuity of air pollution data over time. Some of the air pollution monitoring stations that provide PM₁₀ input data for the forecast model may experience technical issues and fail to deliver data for several days or even months, disabling the service from issuing forecasts for those locations. The CAMS Data Store service was also down following a data server migration, preventing the release of the forecast on certain dates.
- Technical disturbances were caused by migration of the data servers involving changes in the programming interfaces and data format, delaying the implementation of the service.

4.1.3. Ways forward

For the upcoming years it is important to guarantee and expand the air pollution observation network on which the AUROARE service relies, especially in the Arctic. The EEA and FMI are operating only a few stations at latitudes north of 65°N; expanding the in situ observation network is essential to improve the knowledge on air pollution in remote areas and increase the geographical extension of the AURORAE service. The extension of geographical coverage of the in situ monitoring stations would allow the production of forecasts on a regular geographical grid.

Currently, most of the EEA and FMI stations measure PM₁₀ concentrations, but only a small amount of them can measure the concentrations of other key pollutants such as PM_{2.5}, ozone, nitrogen oxides, and sulfur oxides, etc. It is essential to increase the analytical capabilities of the in situ monitoring stations to provide more data on such other atmospheric pollutants and to develop a comprehensive forecast model including those compounds.

Continuous engagement and collaboration with local communities, local authorities and citizens is crucial also to increase the usefulness of the service and to provide socio-economic benefits to the users. In addition, there is a strong relationship between air pollution and wildfires, especially in Canada and Alaska. A future expansion of the AURORAE service to North America would constitute a valuable opportunity to develop a new service, in collaboration with the INFRA service, that provides information on both wildfire activities and the level of air pollution generated by such extreme events, improving communities' responsiveness and mitigation capabilities.

4.2. WMO GTS datasets made available

Norwegian Meteorological Institute (MET)

4.2.1. Background

The World Meteorological Organisation (WMO) Global Telecommunication System (GTS) is the system serving real time exchange of data for WMO and is operated in a private network. It is a key component of the WMO Information System (WIS). GTS is being replaced by a more modern approach, WIS2.0, based on an approach relying on a lightweight, publish-subscribe, machine to machine network protocol for message queue/message queuing service (MQTT). When the transition from GTS to MQTT is finished, the WMO real time exchange of data will no longer happen in a private network but will use the public Internet as the transport mechanism. It is, however, still a private network in the sense that it is made to serve the needs of WMO member states operational services. (Details on the system set up are provided through the acronym list in Appendix 2)

Traditionally, the GTS information has been conveyed in WMO binary formats BUFR and GRIB which are generally difficult formats to interpret, requiring specialised software and correct lookup tables. WIS2 is detaching a bit from the BUFR and GRIB approach, making the information easier to read and interpret (although the bulk of data will still be in these formats). As part of the evolution of WMO data exchange, the Climate and Forecast metadata convention CF-NetCDF has also become a WMO adopted format and can be used in WIS2.0.

While GTS focused primarily on real time or near real time data, WIS2.0 has a wider scope and will also be able to serve delayed mode data (although this capacity is still under development). MQTT in WIS 2.0 is a direct replacement for GTS in the real time data exchange capacity. Furthermore, with the existing GTS operation through private networks (as opposed to Internet), there is a need for user community demand for the products, for e.g. feeding into numerical models, as bandwidth is limited.

4.2.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Arctic PASSION has contributed to making real time exchange data within the WMO GTS available for non-GTS connected users. Data were extracted from WMO BUFR binary data format and converted to CF-NetCDF format for publication. In the process, individual measurements were aggregated into datasets. The intention was also to ingest datasets into WMO GTS, but no datasets were proven to be relevant for real-time exchange at this point. Delayed mode datasets will be continuously considered for this purpose. The datasets extracted from WMO GTS were not, as such, generated by Arctic PASSION, but the project improved and simplified access to these data for a larger number of

users by exposing them outside the limited group that have access to them today. Furthermore, by ingesting them into the SAON data portal the datasets were made more easily discoverable.

The datasets generated by Arctic PASSION based on information through WMO GTS are published as CF-NetCDF files with global attributes adhering to the Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery (ACDD). In the process, the instantaneous measurements reported as messages in WMO channels were collocated into time series as well.

The primary focus of the approach, in prioritized order, was to extract information from synoptic weather stations, radiosonde stations and ocean buoys. More than 45 weather stations were made available, and about 20 radiosonde stations. The number of reporting ships and buoys is highly variable.

For the ingestion of new datasets, a challenge was that no new (near) real time data streams announced by Arctic PASSION partners that would be suitable. Nor were any third-party datasets identified as suitable for ingestion and subsequent use by e.g. the WMO modelling community. Although the availability of real time or near real time observations from the Arctic is improving, the business model of research is still imposing bottlenecks for swift data publication and data reuse. Thus, no real-time data was made available for WMO GTS or MQTT (interface not available).

4.2.3. Ways forward

Work is in progress to make discovery metadata from the SAON Data Portal available for WIS 2.0, to announce the existence of new data as such become available. This is not ingestion into the real time exchange of data (as discussed above) but merely adapting the discovery metadata announcing the existence of a dataset to the discovery mechanism of WIS 2.0. The reason for this is that WIS 2.0 relies on a totally different discovery protocol than what is normally used within scientific data management. This interface contains both data generated by Arctic PASSION partners and third-party datasets. While National Meteorological and Hydrological Services within WMO are providing much data at low and mid latitudes it is observed that most of the data in the Polar regions come from the research community. Encouraging this community to continuously improve real time data access by sharing with operational agencies would be beneficial but also calls for alternative business models for the research community. While shared datasets are increasingly acknowledged as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), they often still remain less emphasized compared to more traditional metrics.

4.3. Radiation observations over the ocean

Italian National Research Council, Institute of Polar Sciences (CNR-ISP)

4.3.1. Background

Reduction in sea ice extent and thickness largely impacts surface energy exchange processes. Response of the clouds to the changing surface conditions modify the planetary albedo when sea ice melts. Knowledge of all processes and interactions is still poor, with systematic measurements almost exclusively made only from space while ground-based observations are very few and sporadic. This limitation has an impact also on the quality of satellite measurements due to the lack of data for validation activities using observations over the ocean and at high latitudes.

4.3.2. Evolution and lessons learned through Arctic PASSION

Arctic PASSION continued an activity initiated under the ARICE framework, taking the opportunity provided by the PONANT cruise operators to implement a cost-effective monitoring programme for surface radiation fluxes and cloud measurements over the Arctic Ocean. The programme was designed with both scientific and technical objectives.

From a scientific perspective, continuous radiation and sky observations allow characterization of downwelling radiation at the surface. These cover both shortwave (SW) and longwave (LW) components, as well as cloud coverage and radiative impact over a very wide range of latitudes through the whole summer season. Measurements of UV-A and UV-B surface fluxes also provide valuable data for investigations of marine ecosystems.

Technically, several new solutions were tested to improve ship-based atmospheric measurements, particularly automatic clean systems for radiometer domes. The goal is to ensure instrumentation continuous operation with minimal maintenance, allowing all cruises to contribute relevant data and potentially transmit them to land in near real time.

In 2022 a suite of sensors for measuring downwelling fluxes and ancillary parameters was installed on the icebreaker cruise ship *Le Commandant Charcot*. Following a detailed inspection and assessment of requirements for radiation measurements, maintenance, power supply, and communication, the instrumentation was mounted aft on the port side of the tenth deck (see Photos 1 and 2).

The sensor suite includes a pyranometer, a pyrgeometer, a UV-A sensor, a UV-B sensor and an all-sky camera. Due to technical issues, only 2-3 months of data were collected in 2022. After repairs and system checks in April 2023, the setup was stabilized, enabling continuous data acquisition from May 2023 to May 2025. During this period, the ship conducted multiple cruises both in Arctic and Antarctic regions. An instrument maintenance and upgrade effort is planned for July 2025.

The acquired datasets support the development of novel analysis methodologies. Additionally, the design of an automatic cleaning system (RADCLEAN) has been initiated, with the first prototype currently under construction.

4.3.3. Ways forward

As the work continues, future plans include:

- Routine observations of radiation and cloudiness conditions aboard *Le Commandant Charcot*.
- Establishing a second observing point on the ship to increase the significance of measurements as recommended by several studies and best practices. CNR-ISP and PONANT will collaborate to identify the most suitable solution for this upgrade.
- Finalizing the RADCLEAN system and conducting extended performance tests.
- Ensuring data interoperability with project database through Italian polar data repositories, particularly IADC.
- Developing methodologies based on the large volume of new data, with a focus on cloudiness.

SPN1	SGR4	MS10S UB-A	MS11S UV-B	AllSkyCam
------	------	---------------	---------------	-----------

Photos: Instrument location and details of instrument mounting on the aft side of Le Commandant Charcot.

5. Establishing a comprehensive Arctic observing system

The objectives of Arctic PASSION all aimed to evolve the current Arctic observing system towards a more coherent and holistic system. We built on recent previous efforts, existing programmes, and parallel collaborative processes - uniting and expanding them, to serve short-term operational to long-term planning needs. The activities were coordinated across disciplines, sectors, communities, and infrastructures. Science and community-based approaches to observing have resulted in both technological and human-centred methods inclusive of Indigenous and Local Knowledge. Major advances were made in establishing joint planning tools, common observation protocols and data processing standards. These efforts benefit the observing community by reducing and sharing operational costs, eliminating redundancies, while optimizing the collection of high-quality data needed for monitoring and understanding Arctic change.

In this chapter we highlight our recommendations for further development, building on the Arctic PASSION outputs within the observational scope outlined in Chapters 2-4. We focus on the four areas: **Priorities for enhancing Arctic observations**, **Technical solutions** to overcome observing challenges, and **Organisational improvements**. These aim to reduce fragmentation, both within system components and across nations, communities and organizations, while supporting **Long-term Sustainability**.

A range of initiatives, launched before and during Arctic PASSION, have significantly advanced the scope of Arctic observations. Below, we briefly introduce some of these efforts before presenting the recommendations based on the contributions by Arctic PASSION in sections 5.1–5.4.

The H2020 project Key Environmental monitoring for Polar Latitudes and European Readiness (KEPLER; Wilkinson et al., 2020; Gabarró et al., 2020) explored how the in situ observational research community could better support the objectives of Copernicus in both the marine and terrestrial domains. There were several gaps identified in the efforts to enhance monitoring and forecasting capabilities in the Polar Regions. Despite Europe having a well-connected and collaborative polar research community there were relatively few established links found between these entities and the Copernicus Services. For over a decade, Copernicus operational polar products have been delivered through the various service components (CMEMS, CLMS, CEMS, C3S, and CAMS), relying heavily on the availability and continuity of both space-based and in situ observations. Any disruption in these data streams risks degrading product quality or even halting services.

In their Arctic Strategy/Policy (European Commission, 2021), the European Union and the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy jointly recognized the need to tackle both challenges and opportunities in the changing Arctic through enhanced coordination and cooperation with Arctic states, regional authorities and local communities. It was highlighted that any EU action should be based on its values and principles, including the rule of law, human rights, sustainable development, gender equality, diversity and inclusion, support for rules-based multilateralism, and the respect of international law. The EU targets set in 2021 within the context of observations was to boost Earth and ocean observation, forecasting and climate prediction, primarily through greater capacity for Copernicus and EMODnet to better anticipate the effects of global warming and extreme weather events.

Recommendations from the H2020 project Integrated Arctic Observation System (INTAROS; Sandven et al., 2022) called for future observing systems adaptable to shifting priorities, emerging requirements, and technological advancements, in continuous dialogue among local communities, public and private stakeholders, researchers, and service providers. INTAROS identified a key difference in the development and sustainability of in situ versus space-based observing systems,

attributing this largely to differences in funding mechanisms at national, European, and international levels.

To strengthen coordination across polar activities, the European Commission established the Copernicus Polar Task Force of external experts in 2022. This group aims to guide the integration of Copernicus services with existing space assets, in situ data, and modelling capabilities. Their work has resulted in e.g. the Copernicus Polar Roadmap for Service Evolution ('CS Polar Roadmap'; Duchossois et al., 2024), underscoring the critical need for additional and sustained in situ observations, which remain sparse across the polar regions. This scarcity presents a significant gap, particularly for the context of validation and verification of products and in the assimilation of data into models. The roadmap also highlighted the need for continued scientific research to advance our understanding of polar physical and biogeochemical processes, improve algorithms, and develop more sophisticated data assimilation and forecasting models - particularly for sea ice, ice sheets, and glaciers.

The EU-PolarNet 2 project conducted a comprehensive research prioritisation process for identifying key Polar research actions (Venier et al., 2023). Twenty research topics (often applicable to both poles) were extracted for the four scopes of Polar climate system, Polar biodiversity and socio-economic system, Human impacts on polar system, and Prospering Communities in the Arctic. EU-PolarNet 2 also presented over eighty actionable recommendations across seven pillars aimed at enhancing cooperation in observing the polar regions (Lymer et al., 2024). This offered specific guidance for Arctic and Antarctic observations, and tailored recommendations for the European Commission to strengthen collaboration in polar observations within and beyond the EU.

In its Key Trends and Impacts report (AMAP, 2024), the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme presents updated findings on climate change indicators in the Arctic, including extreme events, Arctic–midlatitude linkages, landscape hydrology, ocean acidification, and cryosphere changes. The report offers recommendations for both policy and science, with a strong emphasis on Indigenous involvement. Of equal importance, this work demonstrates the value of observational data in assessments addressing societal needs and climate adaptation.

In the following, **key messages from the observing community in Arctic PASSION are given in bold font** to allow easy identification in the running text. Where relevant, we relate to and reiterate recommendations from previous efforts.

5.1. Priorities for enhancing Arctic observations

The Arctic Ocean is still severely under-observed. Significant steps have been taken through Arctic PASSION to enhance coverage and improve coordination of ocean field campaigns, harmonize procedures, and align priorities for key variables.

Key 'interfaces', like the land-coast and sea ice-upper ocean boundaries as well as regional hotspots of rapid change, should be covered by continuous, long-term, inter-disciplinary monitoring programmes, covering an agreed minimum set of indicators. For example, the pan-Arctic network of Distributed Biological Observatories (PAN-DBO), located in the key gateways and regions of rapid change in the Arctic marine domain, works towards building consistent time series through standardised in situ sampling of key indicators within fundamental biogeochemistry such as chlorophyll and light, nutrients, oxygen, carbon system variables, distribution of zooplankton and fish, and benthic biodiversity and abundance, relevant for ecosystem evaluations.

For the sea ice domain, merging manned in situ work with autonomous observations is a key step toward improving time series records. Even minimally maintained drifting sea ice stations can significantly enhance data quality and reduce uncertainties. The ability to revisit these stations and supplement autonomous data with manned observations adds substantial value.

These actions agree with and expand those given in the CS Polar Roadmap (Duchossois et al., 2024) where in situ data on snow and sea ice parameters, essential physical variables like salinity and temperature, and key biogeochemical indicators such as pH and oxygen, are especially emphasized. These data would not only be used for validating space observations but also provide data and insights that cannot be obtained from space.

Community-based monitoring of change should be expanded with observations led by those with deep cultural and local knowledge, along with mechanisms established to highlight “significant change” as interpreted by CBM co-researchers.

For the future, it is essential to ensure the sustainability of the observations feeding into services developed in Arctic PASSION. **Expanding both satellite and in situ observation networks, particularly in remote and less monitored areas, will enhance the accuracy and comprehensiveness of the services.** For example, in the Lake Ice Service, incorporating Copernicus Higher-Resolution Water Snow Ice data expected by 2026, will improve details for smaller water bodies and enable more effective monitoring during the polar night, which is crucial for the Arctic region. Continued **collaboration with indigenous and local communities will be important to maintaining the relevance and usefulness of the services**, see also 5.3. For the INFRA Wildfire Service, a goal is to increase the number of observations systems used by the service, such as incorporating information provided by Copernicus Atmospheric services (CAMS). In addition, **local communities, rights-holders and end users should be increasingly involved** in the development of the functionality and documentation of the service and, perhaps even more importantly, in incorporating local knowledge and information in the overall information flow of the service.

Arctic PASSION supported the identification and selection of Shared Arctic Variables for Wildfire, Permafrost, and Sea Ice. Expert Panels for each theme include representatives from Indigenous communities, policy, and academia to ensure SAVs reflecting essential observational needs. For Wildfire, work on SAV definitions was undertaken in both Finland and North America. The work progressed more rapidly in Finland due to already existing contacts and networks, defining **Wildfire Ignition Identification as a SAV to first implement in Finland, and thereafter in other Nordic Countries, and in North America.** For Permafrost, the SAV definition progressed to the end of the second phase of the ROADS-defined process, with **Permafrost temperature and Active layer thickness proposed as SAVs.** These variables are already Essential Climate Variables but would serve, as SAVs, to expand the scope to perspectives of Arctic Indigenous Peoples, medical sciences and social sciences. **A third Permafrost SAV, related to changes in wellbeing resulting from changes in the permafrost and other parts of the environment, was proposed for further consideration.** For Sea Ice, an Expert Panel pilots the SAON ROADS process in the Baffin Bay region now working to **conclude the initial assessment of needed Arctic sea ice observations to strengthen the existing observational networks in the region while prioritizing societal benefit for Arctic coastal communities.** In general, two more SAV themes are currently worked upon; Harmful Algal Blooms (focus across Alaska’s marine regions) and Salmon and Food Security (focus on Bristol Bay, Alaska), both with established Expert Panels (D6.3). **It is vital that Expert Panel work for all themes is sustained, to support community-driven decision-making** within the areas of broad concern that the SAV themes represent.

EU-PolarNet 2 (Lymer et al. 2024) recommended continued enhancement of the complementarity between in situ and remote observations across scales (particularly for calibration and validation

efforts), and expansion of coupled satellite observations for addressing in situ data gaps, in collaborative efforts with the European Space Agency. A specific example of such enhancement raised by the Arctic PASSION team was to collect more high-quality ground reference data, needed to improve the performance of satellite-based Ice Surface Temperature retrievals. The way forward is to **increase the number of high-quality sea ice buoys to much larger numbers than are currently available.**

Dialogue between the KEPLER project (Wilkinson et al., 2020) and the marine and terrestrial observational communities highlighted the need for stronger engagement with Copernicus Services. In particular, KEPLER emphasized the value of in situ data for calibrating and validating Copernicus products in polar regions and called for broader involvement of the European polar research community beyond existing links with Thematic Assembly Centres (TACs). Arctic PASSION made meaningful progress, especially in advancing in situ contributions for validation. **Continued efforts to strengthen collaboration with Copernicus Services remain essential to fully realize the potential of integrated polar observations.**

5.2. Technical and practical solutions

At land monitoring sites, future efforts to standardise complex ecosystem indicators could benefit from the lessons learned during Arctic PASSION's implementation of harmonised climate variable monitoring. This requires **enhanced support for capacity-building and maintenance, while technical coordination is essential, alongside innovations such as data quality checks and automation assisted by Artificial Intelligence.** Although representatives from terrestrial and marine monitoring networks, such as INTERACT and the DBOs, have met and exchanged experiences through Arctic PASSION, **there is still untapped potential for more systematic collaboration across the land and ocean domains.**

For Land ice, a goal is to develop a scalable AI-driven tool for near-real-time glacier calving front monitoring using publicly available satellite data from NASA, ESA and other space agencies. Commercial satellite imagery does exist but would be prohibitively expensive for operational applications. The envisioned tool development aligns with the initiatives like the ESA AI4EO program and the NASA Earth System Observatory. **A longer-term goal is to build an integrated digital twin for Arctic land ice that combines Earth Observation data, numerical models, and AI.** This aligns with the EU Destination Earth and ESA DTE initiatives.

In the marine realm, **the use of autonomous systems should be expanded to improve coverage of underobserved areas and seasons, such as the sea-ice obstructed upper ocean, and winter.** Inter-disciplinary sea-ice based sensor platforms covering atmosphere, snow, sea ice and the upper ocean should be further developed and deployed systematically. **Increasing the number of high-quality platforms is essential** not only for collecting key in situ data, but also to support calibration and validation of satellite and model products and enabling service development.

Ecosystem observations should be expanded through increased use of ecologically relevant sensors, alongside continued sensor development. Advances in broadband satellite communications in the high Arctic now enable deployment and operation of data-intensive instruments (e.g. multibeam echosounders and broadband passive acoustic sensors) with drifting sea ice platforms. **These integrated sensors suites should be deployed routinely to help cover essential data gaps in the sea ice-upper ocean interface, particularly within the ecosystems scope.**

Further improvements and ways forward on the technical/practical side include **arranging for additional ship time to test autonomous systems on site right after deployment and to efficiently combine sea ice buoy deployments with deployments of other autonomous equipment.** With a

growing number of costly instrument packages being deployed, their recovery becomes more important. This calls for **improved coordinated capacity and co-developed recovery plans for deployed sea ice sensor stations and other autonomous equipment.**

The KEPLER project (Gabarró et al., 2020) highlighted the importance of acquiring High Priority Environmental Parameters for sea ice, land ice, and snow, particularly in preparation for upcoming satellite missions. EU-PolarNet 2 (Lymer et al. 2024) called for the adoption of unmanned systems and smarter technologies to enhance both space-based and real-time Earth observations. Similarly, the CS Polar Roadmap (Duchossois et al., 2024) encouraged the development of novel in situ platforms through international collaboration and private-sector partnerships. While Arctic PASSION made some progress in these areas, further efforts are needed to fully realize these ambitions.

Updated sea ice information for ships navigating in ice infested waters can be provided by improved satellite Risk Index Outcome products based on interpreted satellite data, made available a few hours after satellite overpass. **To increase the useability of POLARIS forecast information, higher-resolution regional models need to be developed to provide sea ice forecast information at the required spatial scale.** The IMO plans should be followed to revise and improve the POLARIS methodology. **The collection of POLARIS information from ships should be coordinated** to support the validation and development of the methodology, including error assessment.

An under-ice acoustic geopositioning and navigation network should be established, covering all basins of the central Arctic Ocean. This will allow ARGO profilers, gliders and endurance AUVs to operate there year-round. The acoustic network should comprise both low-frequency sound sources installed on bottom-anchored moorings and shorter-range two-way transceiver units attached to drifting sea ice. The latter can both provide accurate position data for under-ice platforms and relay data between the platforms and land via satellite. The EU-funded HiAOOS project has deployed an acoustic mooring network in the Nansen and Amundsen Basins for 2024 to 2026, and this should be sustained and expanded beyond that project. Similar infrastructure is deployed in the Beaufort Sea, and **the sound sources of these two systems should be aligned, with the goal of creating a pan-Arctic acoustic geopositioning and communication network.**

Routine atmospheric observations of radiation and cloudiness conditions should be made from vessels operating regularly in the central Arctic Ocean (as was done e.g. on *Le Commandant Charcot* during Arctic PASSION). Ideally, there should be more than one observing point on each vessel to increase significance of the measurements. Data interoperability should be ensured through polar data repositories, and the resulting large amount of new data should be used for development of improved cloudiness algorithms.

There is a strong relationship between air pollution and wildfires, especially in Canada and Alaska. A future expansion of the AURORAE air pollution service to the North American Arctic would be a valuable opportunity to collaborate with the INFRA service to **develop a coupled service that provides information on both wildfire activities and fire-related air pollution levels, improving the responsiveness and mitigation capabilities of stricken communities.**

INTAROS (Sandven et al., 2022) recommended that for enhancing the capacity and capability of in situ systems, challenges in the data delivery chains must be addressed and transitioned toward a more operational model (this also concerns the ‘business models’ which are different between various systems, affecting data availability). Achieving this requires improved dialogue among all involved actors: researchers, technology providers, data managers, and end users. The CS Polar Roadmap (Duchossois et al., 2024) highlighted the need for smarter ways to process and integrate data from different sources, like satellites and sensors on the ground.

Advances in signal processing, and data science/AI are needed to improve the overall quality of combined Earth observations in polar regions, particularly targeting sea ice related products. **A major challenge is still the lack of comprehensive, permanent, and well-maintained repositories for polar in situ data, and especially for sea ice, designed to support operational applications.**

5.3. Organisational improvements

5.3.1. Observing system components

For land monitoring systems, Arctic PASSION showed that metadata standardisation and virtual access to metadata are achievable through dialogue and mutual learning. Continued support for such collaborative networks is critical to improve data quality and coverage. To build on the momentum gained through the successful implementation in Arctic PASSION, **future land monitoring systems should invest in continued harmonisation of measurements** while respecting site-specific constraints, particularly where integrating new instruments into nationally managed infrastructure remains difficult. **Long-term sustainability of terrestrial monitoring sites requires both interoperable, publicly accessible data, and stable funding to maintain the observing equipment over time.**

The Lake Ice Service should be integrated more thoroughly into a broader Arctic observing system that includes both natural and socio-economic data, facilitating better decision-making across various sectors. Linking ice data with weather, hydrology, and transportation systems could help create a more comprehensive and resilient observing system - ultimately serving society better.

Figure 6. Terrestrial and marine observational networks that were strengthened and better integrated through work supported by Arctic PASSION (Image courtesy of H.Abbas/GridA).

For Land ice, one goal is to **develop a comprehensive meltwater discharge in situ observation network and a high-resolution modelling framework for Arctic glaciers and ice caps**. This aligns with current EU-funded projects, like LIQUIDICE. Also, a collaborative framework for harmonisation of data for Arctic glaciers and ice sheets should be developed for improved integration of national and international initiatives.

In the marine domain, improved coordination of plans for scientific monitoring and dedicated campaigns can be achieved through open annual meetings between actors operating Arctic Ocean scientific expeditions, moorings and sea ice platforms. Ideally, such meetings should have multi-year planning horizons to allow for upcoming project proposals to adjust to known programmes and plans. The cost of deploying marine and sea ice observing infrastructure is often larger than the purchasing cost - improved coordination can help minimize the overall cost.

Along similar lines, EU-PolarNet 2 (Lymer et al. 2024) recommended further development of international agreements for sharing national infrastructures, to facilitate international access and exchanges between polar observatories. Practical actions suggested for implementing these recommendations include extending the use of catalogues such as the Registry of Polar Observing Networks (RoPON) and the Polardex interactive polar infrastructure registration database. **In this context, the GOOS and SAON supported establishment of an Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance (ArORA), currently undertaken by the ArORA Task Team, is vital for bringing together and supporting coordinated Arctic Ocean observing efforts.**

Future observational systems will need to realize a larger proportion of integrated measurements of physical, biological and geochemical parameters compared to earlier setups, for relating changes in the different systems to causes and impacts in the others.

It is important to continue and expand the air pollution observation network, especially in the Arctic region (north of 65°N), to improve the knowledge on air pollution in remote areas and increase the geographical extent of the AURORAE service. The analytical capabilities of the in situ monitoring stations must be developed, to provide more data on additional atmospheric key pollutants, allowing development of more comprehensive forecast models.

The CS Polar Roadmap (Duchossois et al., 2024) highlights the importance of engaging local populations through citizen science to strengthen polar monitoring and support inclusive decision-making. Outreach and demonstration projects play a key role in raising awareness and encouraging participation. Several of the pilot Arctic Services developed within Arctic PASSION (WP4) exemplify this approach. As part of the implementation phase of the Wildfire SAV [2.3] a mobile phone application will be developed to collect terrain moisture observations from individuals walking in nature, contributing to wildfire-related moisture monitoring. A goal for the INFRA Wildfire Service [2.4], is to increasingly involve local communities, rights-holders and end users in the development of the service. Another example is the Lake Ice Service for Arctic Climate and Safety [2.8], which integrates community-based real-time reporting of ice conditions directly from the field, making the service more responsive and contextually relevant. Overall, the Arctic Services developed in the project are grounded in increased engagement and enhanced exchange of knowledge and information with local communities. Each of them represents meaningful contributions to Arctic monitoring that merit continued development.

5.3.2. Coordination across organizational structures

Efforts to synthesise research and integrate observations from diverse knowledge systems should be supported to sustain data use across different observatories and observational approaches. **Different stakeholders should be brought closer together to increase the use of variables or samples**

of special importance for certain user groups. **The work on FAIR and CARE data handling should be continued to improve the usability and accessibility of collected data** and ensure that data collected in the Arctic is used and shared in accordance with the rights holders. Hence, **data management that enables identification, harvesting and use of data across storage platforms should always be encouraged.**

For the marine domain, **closer collaboration is encouraged between the in situ, remote sensing and modelling communities to optimize the availability of data** for validation, evaluation and model input. At the same time, digital tools such as numerical models and geostatistics can help fill spatial and temporal gaps in the often irregular nature of in situ observations. This dual benefit aligns with the call for better integration of complementary capabilities by INTAROS (Sandven et al., 2021). **Regular international network meetings are necessary within the sea ice buoy community to aid sharing information** on systems design and setup, data processing/interpretation, as well as deployment strategies and opportunities. Such networking could help to establish a shared information and planning tool for upcoming expeditions that allow deployment of autonomous systems. Synergies with existing portals and technical solutions should be explored for optimization, and to improve cross-cutting collaborations between users of similar infrastructure.

Long-term, international agreements on observational contributions to pan-Arctic observatories, such as the DBOs, should be developed. Observations should be optimized to detect changes, including societal use and nature conservation needs and harmonised across sites to facilitate comparison but also capture site specific features. **Active links between research activities and existing observational structures should be promoted**, as they will provide temporal and spatial context to new observations.

As part of the Baffin Bay Distributed Biological Observatory, **the established Community Based Monitoring in Qaanaaq should continue to evolve and maintain the core monitoring activities in collaboration with the local community, for community relevant contexts and needs.** The connection across the North Water Polynya, between the Qaanaaq and Grise Fjord CBM initiatives, is expected to grow through collaborative monitoring efforts. The CBM pilot developed under Arctic PASSION aims to evolve into Pikialasorsuami Nasiffik, a locally driven science hub where researchers can engage with the community to present plans, request assistance and share results while the community can express science needs and propose involvement in future activities.

5.4. Long-term sustainability

The lack of sustained, internationally coordinated funding, combined with the high operational costs of Arctic in situ observations, makes it challenging to maintain comprehensive long-term monitoring programmes. This is especially true in the central Arctic Ocean and at remote land sites. Voluntary coordination efforts among key actors, though often intermittent and project-dependent, can improve efficiency and cost-effectiveness but they do not solve the fundamental lack of sustained funding schemes. **This demand of sustainability cannot be addressed only by the observing community but must also be actively supported by users and funders of such observational data, and funding means need to be better aligned to fit the purpose.**

The Arctic PASSION Funding Recommendations towards a Sustained Arctic Observing System (D7.1) outline the need for better coordinated, integrated, useful and equitable Arctic Observing System. The recommendations are based on input from across all Work Packages of the project. The responses were grouped into three categories: Coordination and governance, Observations, and Data. **Long-term funding emerged as a central requirement — not only for maintaining long-term monitoring,**

but also as a prerequisite for developing observation systems that respond to societal needs and for critical data gaps in cryosphere science.

INTAROS (Sandven et al., 2021) emphasized the need for stronger collaboration among initiatives, institutions, organizations, and nations to secure long-term funding for the establishment and operation of observing systems essential to fulfilling the Joint Statement of Ministers (ASM, 2021). Enhanced collaboration should also aim to support the development of a holistic data ecosystem that includes community-based monitoring and citizen science. Equally important is to ensure transfer of knowledge and expertise through capacity-building activities in relevant observation methods, technologies, and procedures, across generations and genders.

To expand the usefulness of several services developed in Arctic PASSION and enhance their socio-economic benefits, continuous engagement and collaboration with local communities, authorities, and citizens is crucial. Sustaining this engagement requires dedicated, long-term funding.

National Meteorological and Hydrological Services within WMO provide much data at low and mid latitudes, but **most of the data in the Polar regions come from the research community. This community should be encouraged to improve the real time access to data.** Such sharing of data with operational agencies would be highly beneficial but also calls for alternative, sustainable business models for the research community.

Collaborative networks like the marine DBOs serve to optimize observational efforts towards common key elements and counteract fragmentation. The facilitation of diverse meeting places in general, as well as support to early career professionals through travel funds, mobility grants and research projects, is needed to leverage scientific outcomes, and expand the international exchange and training opportunities across observatories and programmes.

In the longer term, **sustainable support is essential to create and operate a pan-Arctic framework that unites Arctic ocean observing efforts.** A current initiative by the ArORA Task Team aims to establish an Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance that would harness the collective potential of national and international initiatives, linking observations from coastal zones to continental shelves and the central Arctic Ocean. Along the same lines, EU-PolarNet 2 (Lymer et al. 2024) put emphasis on the need for continued investments necessary for updating, sustaining, and maintaining the existing polar stations, research vessels and infrastructures. The use and being of such existing polar infrastructure could be further optimized through enhanced collaboration between infrastructure managers, vendors and researchers to enhance standardisation.

As a final, fundamental recommendation, we propose giving higher priority to long-term funding of national and institutionally driven time series collection, alongside collaborative responsibilities and timely data sharing. A larger share of the funding currently spent on Arctic data collection should be allocated to long-term, internationally coordinated efforts. This is essential to ensure consistent, high-quality observations of essential variables and to effectively monitor and respond to rapid climate and environmental change.

Appendix 1. References

Arctic PASSION online sources

New datasets and online data portals and tools: <https://arcticpassion.eu/data/>

Developed Arctic Services: <https://arcticpassion.eu/wp/wp4/>; <https://arcticpassion.eu/arcticwindow/services>

Thematic Factsheets: <https://arcticpassion.eu/groups/FACTSHEETS/>

Arctic PASSION reports

D1.1 Mustonen T, Mustonen K, and Roto J (2022). Report on missing elements for an improved Arctic observing system. Arctic PASSION Deliverable 1.3. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14956338>.

D1.2 Matero I, Sevestre H, Lihavainen H, Larsen JR, Veijola K, Murray M, Strahlendorff M, and Wells T (2025). The definition for the pilot set of Essential Arctic Variables. Arctic PASSION Deliverable 1.2. Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17534236>.

D1.3 Nikolopoulos A, and Sundfjord A (2024) Report on development of website with protocols, planning and reporting tools for the Atlantic-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory network, Arctic PASSION Deliverable 1.3, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14956380>.

D1.4 Godøy Ø (2024). Report on WMO GTS datasets made available for non-GTS connected users and on new datasets ingested into WMO GTS based on user requirements. Arctic PASSION Deliverable 1.4, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14956388>.

D1.5 Li T, Bamber J, Igneczi A (2024). Demonstration of ALI monitoring capabilities based on existing satellite and in situ services, Zenodo, [https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.\[ref not yet available\]](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.[ref not yet available])

D1.6 Danish Meteorological Institute, Dybkjær G, Suhr M, Kolbe W, Singha S, Jensen A, Gierisch A, Kreiner M, Wulff T, Mortensen N, Olsen S, Ribergaard M, and Eastwood S (2025). FRM Surface Temperature Datasets. Arctic PASSION Deliverable 1.6, Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16982595>.

D1.7 Sundfjord A, Kanzow T, Foss Ø, Nicolaus M, Sennechael N, Tomasz PK, Granskog M, Preußner A, von Appen W-J, and Nikolopoulos A (2025). New near-real time data and time series from drifting observatories and new long-term moorings in the interior Arctic. Arctic PASSION Deliverable 1.7, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16880626>.

D4.3 Vitale V (2024). Documentation on the INFRA service and its functionalities (Versjon 1), Arctic PASSION Deliverable 4.3, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17161102>.

D4.7 Irrgang A (2024). GTN-P permafrost observing best practices for WMO Guide (T4.2). Arctic PASSION Deliverable 4.7, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14963159>.

D4.12 Vitale V (2025). Report on development of INFRA as an operational service, new functionalities and performances (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17508229>.

D4.13 Crotti I, Cuzzucoli A, DeMarchi D, Ramalli E, Selmi L, Trandafir I, PASINI A, and Dobricic S (2025). AURORAE service: Model description and forecast delivery for the local atmospheric pollution forecasts, Arctic PASSION Deliverable 4.13, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15864354>.

D6.3 Larsen JR, Bradley AC, Waigl C, Wayner H, Lihavainen H, Matero I, Veijola K, Divine L, Rudolf M, Murray M, Strahlendorff M, Palarto NJ, Starkweather S, and Wells T (2025). Report on SAON Progress in ROADS, Arctic PASSION Deliverable 6.3, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15856556>.

D7.1 Grosfeld L, and Rachold V (2025). Policy support for the Arctic Science Funders Forum, Arctic PASSION Deliverable 7.1, Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15364667>.

D8.2 Karcher M, Wilkinson J, and Sundfjord A (2025). Final Synthesis and Roadmap for further evolution of the pan-AOSS. Arctic PASSION Deliverable 8.2, Zenodo, [https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.\[ref not yet available\]](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.[ref not yet available])

General references

AMAP (2024). AMAP Arctic Climate Change Update 2024: Key Trends and Impacts. Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP), Tromsø, Norway. x+122pp, ISBN 978-82-7971-203-9, <https://www.amap.no/documents/doc/amap-arctic-climate-change-update-2024-key-trends-and-impacts/3851>, and policy summary: <https://www.amap.no/documents/download/7310/inline>

Arctic Science Ministerial (2021). Joint Statement of Ministers On the occasion of the Third Arctic Science Ministerial, Tokyo, Japan, <https://asm3.org>.

Biskaborn BK, Smith SL, Noetzli J et al. (2019). Permafrost is warming at a global scale. *Nat Commun* 10, 264, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-08240-4>.

Bliss LC, Heal OW, and Moore JJ (Editors) (1981). *Tundra Ecosystems: A Comparative Analysis, (International Biological Programme 25)*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, pp. 257–284.

Bradley A, Eicken H, Lee O, Gebruk A, and Pirazzini R (2023). Shared Arctic Variable Framework Links Local to Global Observing System Priorities and Requirements. *Arctic*, 74(5). <https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic76429>.

Callaghan TV, Johansson M, Heal OW, Sælthun NR, Barkved LJ., Bayfield N, (...) Siikamäki P (2004). Environmental Changes in the North Atlantic Region: SCANNET as a collaborative approach for documenting, understanding and predicting changes. *Ambio Special Report*, 13, 35–58.

Duchossois G, Berdahl M, Diehl T, Garric G, Humbert A, Itkin P, Jawak S, and Tietsche S (2024). Copernicus polar roadmap for service evolution, EU Publications Office, Luxembourg, doi:10.2889/644108.

Dybkjær G, Suhr MB, Jensen AET, Singha S (2025). Arctic PASSION - Polar Monthly Mean Ice Surface Temperature (AP-MMIST) for the time period 1982 to 2024 [dataset]. PANGAEA, <https://doi.org/10.1594/PANGAEA.975011>.

European Union (2024). Directive (EU) 2024/2881 of the European Parliament and of the Council 23 October 2024 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe (recast), eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/2881/oj/eng.

European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Crotti I, Cuzzucoli A, De Marchi D, Selmi L, Eyraud F, Ramalli E, Pasini A and Dobricic S (2024). The AURORAE (Air qUality foRecast foR Arctic communitiEs) service, EU Publications Office, Luxembourg, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/5041509>, JRC139867.

European Commission (2021). A stronger EU engagement for a peaceful, sustainable and prosperous Arctic, JOIN (2021) 27 final, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021JC0027>.

Gabarró C et al. (2020). Report on the identified research gaps in terms of space-based capabilities in order to improve the Polar Regions monitoring and forecasting, KEPLER project (Key Environmental monitoring for Polar Latitudes and European Readiness), Deliverable D3.3. [Available at <https://kepler-polar.eu/>]

Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) (2016). Permafrost Essential Climate Variable (ECV) Factsheet. [Available at https://ane4bf-datap1.s3.eu-west-1.amazonaws.com/wmod8_climatedata/s3fs-public/permafrost_ecv_factsheet:_201905.pdf?g.E9WybO2xIDJVXmTENgHHExmy7m3XJe (access date: 01. Dec. 2021)]

Grebmeier JM, Moore SE, Cooper LW, Frey KE (2019). The Distributed Biological Observatory: A change detection array in the Pacific Arctic – An introduction. *Deep Sea Research Part II: Topical Studies in Oceanography* 162:1-7, doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2019.05.005.

Grosse G, Jones B, and Arp C (2013). 8.21 Thermokarst Lakes, Drainage, and Drained Basins. In: Shroder JF (ed.): *Treatise on Geomorphology*, 325–353, Academic Press, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-374739-6.00216-5.

Hjort J, Streletskiy D, Doré G, Wu Q, Bjella K, and Luoto M (2022): Impacts of permafrost degradation on infrastructure. *Nature Reviews and Earth Environment*, 3:24–38, doi: 10.1038/s43017-021-00247-8.

Holmberg A (2022). Statement on Co-Creation. Available at https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_v8ddQQ6iCk.

Hovelsrud GK, Poppel B, van Oort B, and Reist JD (2011): Arctic Societies, Cultures, and Peoples in a Changing Cryosphere. *Ambio*, 40 (Suppl 1):100–110, doi: 10.1007/s13280-011-0219-4.

IDA Science and Technology Policy Institute and Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (2017). International Arctic Observations Assessment Framework. IDA Science and Technology Policy Institute, Washington, DC, U.S.A., and Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks, Oslo, Norway, 73 pp. [Available at <https://arcticobserving.org/images/pdf/misc/STPI-SAON-International-Arctic-Observations-Framework-Report-2017.pdf>]

Inuit Circumpolar Council-Alaska (ICC) (2015). Alaskan Inuit food security conceptual framework: How to assess the Arctic from an Inuit perspective: Summary report and recommendations report. Retrieved from Inuit Circumpolar Council – Alaska. [Available at <https://iccalaska.org/wp-icc/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Food-Security-Summaryand-Recommendations-Report.pdf>]

Jackson K, Wilkinson J, Maksym T, Meldrum DT, Beckers J, Haas C, and Mackenzie D (2013). A Novel and Low-Cost Sea Ice Mass Balance Buoy. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 30(11), 2676-2688, doi: 10.1175/JTECH-D-13-00058.1.

Johansson M, and Callaghan TV (2025). The rise and fall of science diplomacy in the Arctic: The “INTERACT” experience. *Polar Record*, 61, Article e8, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0032247425000014>.

Kolbe W M, Dybkjær G, Tonboe R T, Eastwood S, Nielsen-Englyst P, Høyer J, Toft Jensen A, Barfod Suhr M, 2025. Arctic and Antarctic Surface Temperatures from AVHRR thermal Infrared satellite sensors 1982–2023, Remote Sensing of Environment, Volume 328, 114816, ISSN 0034-4257, doi:10.1016/j.rse.2025.114816.

Krupnik I and Crowell AL (editors) (2020). Arctic crashes: people and animals in the changing north, Washington, Smithsonian Scholarly Press, 2020, 555 pp.

Lantuit H, Overduin PP, and Wetterich S (2013). Recent Progress Regarding Permafrost Coasts. *Permafrost and Periglacial Processes*, 24:120–130, doi:10.1002/ppp.1777.

Liljedahl A, Boike J, Daanen R et al. (2016). Pan-Arctic ice-wedge degradation in warming permafrost and its influence on tundra hydrology. *Nature Geosci* 9, 312–318, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2674>.

Lymer G, Badhe R, Elshout P, Larsen JR, Savela H, Scory S, Spadetto V (2024). White paper with recommendations to accelerate the development of a sustained and fully integrated Polar observing system. EU-PolarNet 2 Deliverable 6.7. [Available at: <https://www.eu-polarnet.eu/>]

Mann PJ, Strauss J, Palmtag J, [12 more authors], and Juhs B (2022) Degrading permafrost river catchments and their impact on Arctic Ocean nearshore processes. *Ambio*, 51:439–455, doi:10.1007/s13280-021-01666-z.

Moore SE and Grebmeier JM (2018) The Distributed Biological Observatory: Linking Physics to Biology in the Pacific Arctic Region, *ARCTIC*, 71, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26646184>.

Nitze I, and Grosse G (2016): Detection of landscape dynamics in the Arctic Lena Delta with temporally dense Landsat time-series stacks, *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 181: 27–41, doi:10.1016/j.rse.2016.03.038.

Nitze I, Lübker T, Pohlabein S, and Grosse G (2025): Pan-Arctic Visualization of Landscape Change (2005-2024), Arctic PASSION Permafrost Service [dataset], PANGAEA. doi:10.1594/PANGAEA.983891.

Noetzli J, Christiansen HH, Hrbacek F, Isaksen K, Smith SL, Zhao L, and Streletskiy DA (2021). Cryosphere; 1) Permafrost thermal state [in "State of the Climate in 2020"]. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 102(8): 42-45. doi:10.1175/BAMS-D-21-0086.1.

Sandven S, Sagen H, Hamre T et al. (2022) Roadmap for a sustainable Arctic Observing System, INTAROS Deliverable 1.10. [Available at <https://intaros.nersc.no/>]

Smith S and Brown J (2009). Assessment of the status of the development of the standards for the Terrestrial Essential Climate Variables - T7 - Permafrost and seasonally frozen ground, *Global Terrestrial Observing System Report* 62, 32p. [Available at <https://library.arcticportal.org/668/>]

Smith SL, O'Neill HB, Isaksen K et al. (2022). The changing thermal state of permafrost. *Nat Rev Earth Environ* 3, 10–23, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43017-021-00240-1>.

Starkweather S, Larsen JR, Kruemmel E, Eicken H, Arthurs D, Bradley AC, Carlo N, Christensen T, Daniel R, Danielsen F, Kalhok S, Karcher M, Johansson M, Jóhannsson H, Kodama Y, Lund S, Murray MS, Petäjä T, Pulsifer PL, Sandven S, Sankar RD, Strahlendorff M, and Wilkinson J (2021). Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks' (SAON) Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems (ROADS), <https://journalhosting.ucalgary.ca/index.php/arctic/article/view/74330> <https://doi.org/10.14430/arctic74330>.

Streletskiy D, Smith SL, Vieira G, Schoeneich P, Hrbacek F, Noetzli J and Irrgang AM (2021). Measurement Recommendations and Guidelines for the Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P), Zenodo, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5973079.

Venier C, Cairns W, Ademollo N, Lo Giudice A, Vitale V, Carlo Barbante C, et al. (2023). Identification report of critical future research needs in the Polar Regions. EU-PolarNet 2 Deliverable 3.5. [Available at: <https://www.eu-polar.net.eu/>]

Walvoord MA and Kurylyk BL (2016). Hydrologic Impacts of Thawing Permafrost—A Review. *Vadose Zone Journal*, 15: 1-20 [vzj2016.01.0010](https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2016.01.0010), <https://doi.org/10.2136/vzj2016.01.0010> .

Ward Jones MK, Pollard WH, and Amyot F (2020). Impacts of degrading ice-wedges on ground temperatures in a high Arctic polar desert system. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, 125, e2019JF005173, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JF005173>.

Wilkinson J, Johansson M, Bracher A, Wagner P, Hughes N, and Samuelsen A (2020). Report on the gaps in terms of in situ observations in order to improve Polar Regions monitoring and forecasting capabilities, KEPLER project (Key Environmental monitoring for Polar Latitudes and European Readiness), Deliverable D3.1. [Available at <https://kepler-polar.eu/>]

WMO (2022). The 2022 GCOS Implementation Plan. GCOS-244, GOOS-272 of the WMO Global Climate Observing System (GCOS) programme. [Available at <https://library.wmo.int/idurl/4/58104>]

Appendix 2. Abbreviations, Acronyms and Links

Arctic PASSION	EU H2020 project Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems: Implementing Observations for Societal Needs	https://arcticpassion.eu/ grant agreement No. 101003472
	Descriptions of the project's ten Work Packages (WPs)	https://arcticpassion.eu/wp
	The project's Data Website for download of many of the services and data products	https://arcticpassion.eu/data/
ACDD	Attribute Convention for Dataset Discovery	https://wiki.esipfed.org
A-DBO	Atlantic-Arctic Distributed Biological Observatory	https://arcticpassion.eu/adbo
ALEX	Arctic Landscape Explorer service	See [2.6], https://alex.awi.de
AMAP	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme	https://www.amap.no/
AOS	Arctic Observing Summit	https://arcticobservingsummit.org
ArCS I & II	Arctic Challenge for Sustainability projects	https://www.nipr.ac.jp/arcs2/e/index.html
Arctic GEOSS	ARCTIC GEOSS Global Earth Observations for the Arctic	https://arcticgeoss.org/
Arctic ROOS	EuroGOOS Arctic Regional Ocean Observing System	arctic.eurogoos.eu
Arctic Seas portal	Snowchange Arctic Seas Portal	http://www.arcticseas.org , https://arcticpassion.eu/arcticwindow/services
ARICE	Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium	https://arice-h2020.eu/ <i>grant agreement 730965</i>
ArORA TT	Arctic Ocean Regional Alliance Task Team	https://goosocean.org/arora-task-team
ASM	Arctic Science Ministerial	https://asm3.org
AURORAE	Air Quality Forecast for Arctic Communities	See [4.1]; https://aurorae.azurewebsites.net
BGOS	Arctic Observing Network (AON) Beaufort Gyre Observing System (BGOS)	https://www2.whoi.edu/site/beaufortgyre/ https://arcticdata.io/catalog/portals/beaufortgyre
BUFR	WMO Binary Universal Form for the Representation of meteorological data	https://community.wmo.int
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service	https://climate.copernicus.eu
C3S Ice TAC	Copernicus Climate Change Service Thematic Assembly Centre for Sea Ice	https://marine.copernicus.eu/about/producers/se-aiice-tac
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service	https://atmosphere.copernicus.eu
CARE	Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics; Data principles for Indigenous Data Governance	https://www.gida-global.org/
CBM	Community Based Monitoring	https://arcticcouncil.dspace7.dspace-express.com/handle/11374/141
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service	https://emergency.copernicus.eu
CF	Climate and Forecast metadata convention	https://cfconventions.org
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	https://land.copernicus.eu
CMEMS	Copernicus Marine Environment Monitoring Service	https://marine.copernicus.eu/
CMDS	CMS Copernicus Marine Data Store	https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/ARCTIC_ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_002_001/description
CMS	Copernicus Marine Service	https://marine.copernicus.eu/
CWFIS	Canadian Wildland Fire Information System	https://cwfis.cfs.nrcan.gc.ca/

DBO	Distributed Biological Observatory	https://dbo.cbl.umces.edu (Pacific Arctic Sector)
DMI HYCOM CICE model	North Atlantic - Arctic Ocean coupled HYCOM ocean CICE sea ice model at DMI	https://ocean.dmi.dk/models/hycom.uk.php
ECMWF S2S	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts project for Sub-seasonal to seasonal (S2S) prediction	https://www.ecmwf.int/en/research/projects/s2s
EAV, ECV	Essential Arctic Variables, Essential Climate Variables	https://gcos.wmo.int/site/global-climate-observing-system-gcos/essential-climate-variables
EEA	European Environmental Agency	https://www.eea.europa.eu
EMODnet	European Marine Observation and Data Network	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu
Expert Panel	ROADS Expert Panels (EPs)	https://roadsadvisorypanel.org/expert-panel
ERC	European Research Council	https://erc.europa.eu
ESA	European Space Agency	https://www.esa.int
EU	European Union	https://european-union.europa.eu
EU PolarNet	Co-ordinating and Co-designing the European Polar Research Area	https://eu-polarnet.eu
EuroGOOS	European Global Ocean Observing System	https://eurogoos.eu
CBM Event Database	Event Database of CBM Using Oral Histories, Indigenous knowledge and local knowledge	https://www.arcticseas.org/
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable	Data principles; https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18
FPIC	The practice of Free, Prior and Informed Consent	https://www.ohchr.org/en/indigenous-peoples
FRM	Fiducial Reference Measurements	See [3.2]
G3W	Global Greenhouse Gas Watch	https://g3w.wmo.int/
GCOS	Global Climate Observing Systems	https://gcos.wmo.int/
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System	https://goosocean.org
GRIB	WMO GRIdded Binary (model output and forecasts)	https://community.wmo.int
GrIS-GEUS	Greenland Ice Sheet mass balance service	https://doi.org/10.22008/FK2/OHI23Z
GTN-P	Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost	https://gtnp.arcticportal.org/
GTS	WMO Global Telecommunication System	https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas
GWIS	Global Wildfire Information Service	https://gwis.jrc.ec.europa.eu
HiAOS	EU Horizon Europe project High Arctic Ocean Observing System project	https://hiaaos.eu <i>grant agreement No.101094621</i>
HR-WSI	Copernicus Higher-Resolution Water Snow Ice data	https://www.copernicus.eu/en/access-data
IASC	International Arctic Science Committee	https://iasc.info
IASC MWG	IASC Marine Working Group	https://iasc.info/working-groups/marine
ICC	Inuit Circumpolar Council-Alaska	https://iccalaska.org
IICWG	International Ice Charting Working Group	https://nsidc.org/iicwg
Ice Logistics Portal, ILP	The Global Ice Charts and Sea Ice Information Portal	https://www.icelogistics.info
IMB	Ice Mass Balance buoys	See [3.2]
IMO	International Maritime Organization	https://www.imo.org
INFRA	Integrated Fire Risk Management web service	See [2.4]; https://www.programmaricercaar-tico.it/en/integrated-fire-risk-management-infra-service

INTAROS	EU H2020 project INTEgrated ARctic Observation System	https://intaros.nersc.no <i>grant agreement No. 727890</i>
INPA, INTERACT	International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic Non-Profit Association	https://www.interactassociation.org
IST	Ice Surface Temperature	See [3.2]
K-AWARE	Korea-Arctic ocean WArming & Response of Ecosystem project	https://kopri.re.kr
KEPLER	EU H2020 project Key Environmental monitoring for Polar Latitudes and European Readiness	https://kepler-polar.eu <i>grant agreement No. 821984</i>
Lake Ice Service	Lake Ice component in the Tarkka service and Syke's Earth Observation	See [2.8]; https://tarkka.syke.fi/eo-tarkka/map/
LIQUIDICE	Linking and QUantifying the Impacts of climate change on inland ICE project	https://eu-liquidice.eu/
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport standard messaging protocol	https://mqtt.org
NABOS	Nansen and Amundsen Basins Observational System	https://uaf-iarc.org/nabos
NSF	US National Science Foundation	https://www.nsf.gov
PANGAEA	Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science	https://www.pangaea.de
Polardex	interactive polar infrastructure database	https://polardex.org
POLARIS	IMO Polar Operational Limit Assessment Risk Indexing System	https://www.imo.org
RIO	POLARIS Risk Index Outcome	See [3.3]
ROADS	Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems	https://roadsadvisorypanel.org
RoPON	The Registry of Polar Observing Networks	https://polarobservingregistry.org
SAON, SAON data portal	Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks	https://arcticobserving.org , https://data.arcticobserving.org
SAS	Synoptic Arctic Survey	https://synopticarcticsurvey.w.uib.no
SAV	Shared Arctic Variable	https://roadsadvisorypanel.org ; Bradley et al. 2023
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System	https://sios-svalbard.org
TRUSTED	Towards fiducial Reference measurements of Sea-Surface Temperature by European Drifters	https://www.eumetsat.int/TRUSTED
WIS, WIS 2.0	WMO Information System	https://community.wmo.int/en/activity-areas/wis
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation	https://wmo.int